

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

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**Soil-based agroecological policies and measures
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ABSTRACT

This deliverable aims to identify similarities and differences in the soil health strategies and policy instruments adopted in the seven countries participating in the INTO-dialogue project. Five policy areas which are considered to be consistent with the principles of agroecology and have potential positive impacts on the sustainable agricultural soil management have been analysed in more detail. The document therefore provides an analytical framework and insights which can be useful to support the decisions of policy makers, farmers and other key stakeholders at both national and local levels.

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Table of acronyms and abbreviations

AECM	Agri-environment-climate Measure
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
AT	Agricultural transition
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EC	European Commission
EIP-Agri	European Innovation Partnership - Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
FSN	Food Security and Nutrition
GAEC	Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition
GPP	Green Public Procurement
IPARD	Instrument for pre-accession Assistance
MS	Member State
OG	Operational Group
PDO	Protected Designation of origin
PGI	Protected Geographical Indication
PPP	Polluter Pays Principle
SMR	Statutory Management Requirement
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
WFD	Water Framework Directive

INTRODUCTION

Within the INTO-DIALOGUE Project, the WP 4 “Participatory initiatives in the formulation of policies on soil-based Sustainable Agroecological Systems” aims to define policy strategies to promote soil-based agroecological approaches in line with the recommendations of the European Green Deal, the Mission Board on Soil Health and Food, and the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The INTO-DIALOGUE proposal states that “Sustainable Agroecological System is, until now, not promoted by specific policies at the EU level. Furthermore, the measures promoted are often ineffective due to overly complex patterns of targeting measures and instruments, making it difficult for national policies to match local priorities”. The Task 4.1 therefore focuses on the evaluation of all current legislation and policies on soil management existing at EU and INTO-DIALOGUE country level, as well as at regional level, with the objective of refuting or confirming this statement by providing scientific evidence. Such an evaluation has been carried out with the participation of the INTO-DIALOGUE partners from the seven Countries involved in the project.

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe the results obtained by the working team involved in the Task 4.1 “Analysis of regional, national, EU and Turkish laws, and competencies to incorporate soil-based principles into their laws” in the analysis of the existing policies and measures dealing with the sustainable soil management in the light of agroecological principles. This report also provides information on the perspectives and research avenues offered to all researchers within the project partnership in order to activate further effective synergies and knowledge exchange. For instance, it provides input for Task 4.2 to investigate how different policy instruments influence the behaviour of local actors and ultimately how they should be further improved to address soil-related challenges in different agricultural regions.

It is worth noting that this deliverable is the result of a two-year iterative process of discussion, research and ongoing fine-tuning in which all interested project partners contributed ideas and input by pooling their expertise, skills and various complementary capabilities. The close collaboration between the project partners was considered essential to overcome language barriers and facilitate the study of policies at the sub-national level.

In addition, an active communication with the EJP Soil WP8 “Science to policy interaction” will ensure result dissemination.

This deliverable is structured as follows: the description of the scope and boundaries of the study, including the normative context and background based on a literature review (chapter 1); the methodology, including the description of the analytical framework for a better understanding of the policies under consideration (chapter 2); the results and discussion (chapter 3), and the conclusions and policy recommendations (chapter 4). Finally, the template used to examine how soil health policies are locally addressed is provided in Annex I, while the lists of OGs, living labs and lighthouses, as well as the infringements related to soil health, are presented in Annexes II, III and IV respectively.

1. SCOPE AND BOUNDARIES OF THE STUDY

1.1 Investigating soil-based agroecological policies

This deliverable focuses on the analysis of soil-based policies designed and implemented in recent years in order to contribute to addressing agroecological land use challenges through the sustainable management of agricultural soils. Specifically, agroecological land use challenges are meant as challenges aimed at counteracting or mitigating agricultural soil degradation phenomena, as well as restoring agricultural soils degraded due to conventional farming practices.

Being the agricultural soil system a fundamental subsystem of the agroecosystem, all agroecological policies should aspire to the condition of “healthy agricultural soil”, namely agricultural soil “capable of supporting the production of food and fibre, to a level and with a quality sufficient to meet human requirements, together with continued delivery of other ecosystem services that are essential for maintenance of the quality of life for humans and the conservation of biodiversity” (Kibblewhite et al., 2007).

The deliverable also provides insights on the concordance between the elements which most shape the policy agenda (i.e., the extend of soil threats, the UE policy targets by 2030 and 2050 the commitments undertaken with international conventions), and the concrete actions already planned and funded in the EU project partner countries (Czech Republic, Latvia, Lithuania, Italy, Spain and Türkiye) that most influence farmers’ choices and behaviour.

The analysis of soil-based agroecological policies has been conducted both at EU level and at country level as the different interventions and measures, often designed top-down within very broad strategic or legal frameworks, are implemented differently at national level. Knowing the areas of convergence or divergence between the policies of different countries, and the reasons for them, means more refined analyses with more useful implications for stakeholders, for example in improving policy instruments according to local needs and priorities.

1.2 The normative context

The EU has the competence to intervene in all areas of environmental policy. The EU soil policy action is indeed based on Article 191 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU), which states in general terms that Union policy aims at preserving, protecting and improving the quality of the environment, protecting human health, a prudent and rational utilisation of natural resources, promoting measures at international level to deal with regional or worldwide environmental problems, and in particular combating climate change¹. In addition, environmental protection requirements must be integrated into the definition and implementation of the Union’s policies and actions, in particular with a view to promoting sustainable development (Art. 11 of the TFEU), and consumer protection requirements must be taken into account (Art. 12). As a general principle, EU law takes precedence over the law of the Member States and requires all bodies of the Member States

¹ As in other crucial policy areas (e.g., the Common agricultural Policy and the Cohesion Policy) where competence is shared between the EU and its Member States, i.e. in accordance with the principle of Subsidiarity the EU will only act if – and to the extent that – the objective of a proposed action cannot be adequately achieved at MS level supranational level. This is not so much because of the transnational nature of the matter to be regulated, but because of the degree of impact that EU legislation or regulation is intended to have.

to fully implement the various provisions of EU law. Since 1972, with the *European Soil Charter*² by the Council of Europe, the European Economic Community (EEC), later renamed the European Community (EC) when it became the first pillar of the newly formed EU in 1993, has drawn attention to the issue of soil, understood not only as a scarce and non-renewable resource, characterised by extremely slow degradation rates and formation and regeneration processes, but also as essential ecosystem for human life and health, agricultural production and valuable services, such as the provision of food, biodiversity, energy and raw materials, carbon sequestration, water purification and infiltration, nutrient regulation, pest control and recreation. For these reasons, “healthy soils are a key enabler to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal such as climate neutrality, biodiversity restoration, zero pollution, healthy and sustainable food systems and a resilient environment”³.

However, according to the European Commission (2021), at EU level “there is currently no binding overarching framework that strategically defines policy priorities or parameters for soil protection. Soil protection outcomes in the other laws are mostly derived as a consequence of delivering environmental objectives that are not explicitly soil focused, such as reducing contamination, offsetting greenhouse gas emissions, and preventing other environmental threats”⁴. In addition, “there is a high risk that the EU will fail some of its own and international commitments such as land degradation neutrality. Therefore, coordinated measures by the EU and Member States are necessary to bring EU soil ecosystems back to healthy condition” (European Commission, 2023).

The lack of a recognised legal status for soil - the kind that already exists for air and water under the EU legislation - is well documented (European Commission, 2021a; European Court of Auditors, 2018). However, a list of 37 legislative, strategic policy and funding instruments at EU level has already been identified as relevant to soil protection (European Court of Auditors, 2021; Ecologic Institute, 2017)⁵ (Table 1).

In order to fill the knowledge gap on soil health, the European Commission published on 5th July 2023 the text of a proposal for a “Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on soil monitoring and resilience (Soil monitoring law)”⁶. It establishes a common soil monitoring

² The *European Soil Charter* is the first EU document to emphasise the importance of soil. Although it is a soft-law document, it emphasises in point 2 that “soil is a limited resource which is easily destroyed” and in point 3 that any land-use planning policy must be conceived in terms of the soil properties and the needs of today’s and tomorrow’s society. Particularly, according to the point 4 “farmers and foresters must apply methods that preserve the quality of the soil”. The influence of the 12 points of the *European Soil Charter* is strongly reflected in the subsequent work of the European Commission on the issue. The reader is referred to their reading at the following link: <https://rm.coe.int/090000168067e296>.

³ The quote is taken from the Document Ref. Ares (2020)6391319 - 05/11/2020. The EU Green Deal refers to the set of proposals adopted by the EC to make the EU’s climate, energy, transport and taxation policies fit for reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels.

⁴ This statement can be found at the web page https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/soil-and-land_en.

⁵ An online inventory of soil protection policy instruments (referred to as the Soil Wiki) was developed under the project “Inventory and Assessment of Soil Protection Policy Instruments in EU Member States” (Ecologic Institute, 2017) and updated under the project “Soils4EU: Providing support in relation to the implementation of the EU Soil Thematic Strategy” in 2019. Soil Wiki can be accessed from this page: https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/eu-soil-observatory-euso/eu-soil-observatory-policy_en.

⁶ COM(2023) 416 final.

framework for all soils on the territory of the MSs, giving them sufficient time (after the entry into force of the Directive) to set up their governance system, implement the soil monitoring system, assess soil health and start implementing measures related to sustainable soil management (in compliance with article 10⁷). When defining the sustainable soil management measures MSs shall take into account the programmes, plans, targets and measures listed in Annex IV as well as the latest existing scientific knowledge including results coming out of the Horizon Europe Mission a Soil Deal for Europe.

Furthermore, in order to address the pressures on soils and identify the most appropriate measures to maintain or regenerate soil health by taking into account the variety of soil types, the specific local and climatic conditions and the land use or the land cover, MSs must establish soil districts as the basic governance units to manage soils and, in particular, as regards monitoring and assessment of soil health.

Table 1, below, provides an overview of the main strategies, policies and instruments directly or indirectly related to the topic of healthy soil and its sustainable management. Forty-five policy instruments with significant direct and indirect impacts on sustainable soil management have been identified by the authors. This list certainly is certainly not exhaustive, but in order to ensure an adequate level of completeness, the table has been populated by including, and updating where deemed appropriate, all policies already mentioned in three sources: the European Green Deal Roadmap; Annex IV of the Soil Monitoring Law; and the Soil Wiki online inventory. The descriptions given in the table are extracted from the content of the institutional websites. As it can be seen from many of the entries in the table, the EU legislation often refers to the key competences of MSs in the design and implementation of soil-based policy instruments.

⁷ Article 10 states that “*Member States shall take at least the following measures, taking into account the type, use and condition of soil: a) defining sustainable soil management practices respecting the sustainable soil management principles listed in Annex III to be gradually implemented on all managed soils and, on the basis of the outcome of the soil assessments carried out in accordance with Article 9, regeneration practices to be gradually implemented on the unhealthy soils in the Member States;(b) defining soil management practices and other practices affecting negatively the soil health to be avoided by soil managers*”.

Tab. 1 - Soil-based legal framework in the EU

Policy Instruments	Description
<u>Action Plan for the Development of Organic Production</u>	<p>The EU Commission has set out a comprehensive organic action plan for the EU (COM/2021/141 final/2), which will aim to achieve the European Green Deal target of 25% of agricultural land under organic farming by 2030. The action plan is broken into three interlinked axes that reflect the structure of the food supply chain and the Green Deal’s sustainability objectives. These are: axis 1 (stimulate demand and ensure consumer trust); axis 2 (stimulate conversion and reinforce the entire value chain); axis 3 (organics leading by example: improve the contribution of organic farming to environmental sustainability).</p> <p>The three axes are supported by 23 actions, including action 18: take steps, to set up, in cooperation with stakeholders, a pilot network of climate positive organic holdings, to share best practices. The specific Horizon Europe mission in the area of Soil Health and Food could contribute to this pilot network in particular through the deployment of living labs and lighthouses and other activities supporting carbon farming.</p>
<u>Adaptation Strategy</u>	<p>The EC adopted its new EU strategy on adaptation to climate change (COM/2021/82 final) on 24th February 2021. The new strategy sets out how the European Union can adapt to the unavoidable impacts of climate change and become climate resilient by 2050. The Strategy has four principal objectives: to make adaptation smarter, swifter and more systemic, and to step up international action on adaptation to climate change. More systemic adaptation requires further development and implementation of adaptation strategies and plans at all levels of governance with three cross-cutting priorities: integrating adaptation into macro-fiscal policy; nature-based solutions for adaptation; local adaptation action.</p>
<u>Biodiversity Strategy</u>	<p>The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 “Bringing nature back into our lives” - COM(2020)380 - states that Healthy and resilient societies depend on giving nature the space it needs. Protecting and restoring biodiversity and well-functioning ecosystems is therefore key to boost our resilience and prevent the emergence and spread of future diseases. Soil and related policies are explicitly mentioned in the section “Addressing land take and restoring soil ecosystems”</p>
<u>CCS Directive</u>	<p>The directive on the geological storage of CO₂ (so-called “CCS Directive”, Directive 2009/31/EC) establishes a legal framework for the environmentally safe geological storage of CO₂ to contribute to the fight against climate change. It covers all CO₂ storage in geological formations in the EU and the entire lifetime of storage sites. It also contains provisions on the capture and transport components of CCS, though these activities are covered mainly by existing EU environmental legislation, such as the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Directive or the Industrial Emissions Directive. The CCS Directive is in place since 2009 and had to be transposed into national law by June 2011.</p>
<u>Circular Economy Package (CEP)</u>	<p>The CEP consists of an EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy (EPCE) that establishes a concrete and ambitious programme of action, with measures covering the whole life-cycle of products: from production and consumption to waste management and the market for secondary raw materials. It includes revised legislative proposals on waste will contribute to “closing the loop” of product lifecycles through greater recycling and re-use and bring benefits for both the environment and the economy. Aiming to keep resources in economic cycles as long as possible, the plan addresses key product value chains: electronics and ICT, batteries and vehicles, packaging, plastics, textiles and food. The key legislative documents relating to the implementation of the EPCE are: Directive 2008/98/EC on waste and repealing certain Directives; Directive 2006/66/EC on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators; Directive 2012/19/EU on waste electrical and electronic equipment; Directive 2001/81/EC on national emission ceilings for certain atmospheric pollutants; the Commission’s Proposals to review the Waste Directives as part of the Circular Economy Package.</p>

<u>Cohesion Fund (CF)</u>	The CF provides support to MSs with a gross national income (GNI) per capita below 90% EU-27 average to strengthen the economic, social and territorial cohesion of the EU. For the 2021-2027 period, the CF (Regulation EU 2021/1058) concerns Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia. The CF supports investments in the field of environment and trans-European networks in the area of transport infrastructure (TEN-T). The investments should be aimed at reducing all forms of pollution, including soil pollution.
<u>Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)</u>	Under the CAP is the set of legislation and practices adopted by the EU to provide a common, unified policy for sustainable agriculture, forestry and rural development. The first measures were introduced in 1962. Since then, the policy has been adapted and developed and has undergone a few reforms. The overall objective is to ensure a stable supply of food, safeguard farmers' income, protect the environment and keep rural areas vibrant. Thus, the CAP 2023-27 is a key tool in reaching the ambitions of the European Green Deal, the Farm to Fork and biodiversity Strategies. Soil, with its multiple functions, is at the heart of agriculture, and production, soil protection and rural land management are intrinsically linked. In the period 2023-2027, the three core elements of the CAP which are most relevant for soil protection and soil management are: the Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition (GAEC) standards, the eco-schemes, and the other various approaches combining a wide range of local and EU-level objectives within the National CAP Strategic Plans (CAP-SPs) and the EU CAP Network, including the EIP-AGRI Operational Groups
<u>Construction Products Regulation (CPR)</u>	The CPR lays down harmonised rules for the marketing of construction products in the EU. The Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 provides a common technical language to assess the performance of construction products. It ensures that reliable information is available to professionals, public authorities, and consumers, so they can compare the performance of products from different manufacturers in different countries. The proposal for a revised CPR - COM(2022) 144 final - was adopted on 30 th March 2022. The proposal regulates only the marketing of construction products, including through incorporating certain environmental features to mirror the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation.
Effort Sharing Decision (ESD)	The ESD (Decision No 406/2009/EC) aimed to reduce emissions from sectors in the EU which are not covered by the Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS). The decision, which covered transport, the building sector, agriculture and waste, set a binding target of 10% emissions reductions from these sectors between 2013 and 2020, which had to be collectively reached by the MSs through national policies and measures. It indirectly addressed certain soil threats, such as soil compaction (e.g. by reducing the amount of passes with heavy machinery for input application and ploughing, reducing stocking rates of livestock to avoid trampling) and soil contamination and biodiversity loss (e.g. through measures to avoid excessive use of N fertilisers or pesticides). The revision of the ESR, i.e. the Regulation (EU) 2018/842, was adopted by the Council on 28 th March 2023, and together with the reform of the Regulation on Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry - Reg. EU 2018/841(LULUCF) - is a key piece of the "Fit for 55" puzzle referred to in Communication COM/2021/550 final.
<u>8th Environmental Action Programme (EAP)</u>	In accordance with Article 192(3) of the TFEU, successive general environment action programmes have guided the development and coordination of Union environment policy and provided the framework for Union action in the field of the environment and climate since 1973. On 2 nd May 2022 the 8 th EAP (Decision EU 2022/591 entered into force, as the EU's legally agreed common agenda for environment policy until 2030. The 8 th EAP aims at accelerating the green transition in a just and inclusive way, with the 2050 long-term objective of 'Living well, within planetary boundaries', already established in the 7 th programme (2014-2020).

<u>Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (EIAD)</u>	<p>The Directive 2011/92/EU, as amended by Directive 2014/52/EU, requires the assessment of the environmental effects of public and private projects that are likely to have significant effects on the environment. It is intended to provide a check on projects before they go forward in order to minimise their negative impact on the environment. This is relevant to soil protection since projects (e.g. infrastructure development) could have negative impacts on soil quality through various threats. Identifying these impacts and potentially less harmful alternatives could result in the developer choosing a method that reduces the impact on soil. The directive explicitly addresses soil as one component of the environment. It also addresses biodiversity, which could include effects of projects on soil biodiversity. Soil threats that can be addressed through the directive include erosion, floods and landslides, loss of soil organic matter, contamination, sealing, compaction and loss of biodiversity.</p>
<u>Environmental Liability Directive (ELD)</u>	<p>The Directive 2004/35/EC established a comprehensive EU-wide liability regime for environmental damage based on the ‘polluter-pays’ principle, in order to prevent and remedy environmental damage. The latter is defined as damage to protected species and natural habitats, to water and to soil. The ELD directly addresses contamination of soils, although only if it reaches a certain threshold (i.e., it poses a significant risk to human health). Indirectly, reduced land or site contamination contributes to improved soil health and quality, and thus might improve soil biodiversity. Furthermore, soils may indirectly benefit from the prevention and remedy of damage to protected species and natural habitats: as soil is one of the physical components that a terrestrial habitat is made of, achieving a favourable conservation status of terrestrial habitats could also contribute towards soils protection.</p>
<u>EU Forest Strategy for 2030</u>	<p>The New EU Forest Strategy for 2030 (COM/2021/572 final) recognises the central and multifunctional role of forests, and the contribution of foresters and the entire forest-based value chain for achieving a sustainable and climate neutral economy by 2050 and preserving lively and prosperous rural areas. It does not have any explicit soil-relevant aims and objectives. However, a positive impact on soils can be expected through the enhanced sustainable forest management. Sustainable forests and agroforestry systems can support healthy soils that provide important ecosystem services (such as flood prevention). They enhance soil quality through increasing soil organic matter and soil biodiversity and reduce the risk of soil erosion and landslides. In addition, reforestation can help to restore soil quality (e.g., after the occurrence of forest fires).</p>
<u>The European Landscape Convention (ELC)</u>	<p>Adopted in Florence (Italy) on 20th October 2000, the ELC is aimed at promoting the protection, management and planning of European landscapes and organising European cooperation on landscape issues. It is the first international treaty to be exclusively concerned with all dimensions of European landscape. It applies to the entire territory of the Parties and relates to natural, urban and peri-urban areas, whether on land, water or sea. It therefore concerns not just remarkable landscapes but also ordinary everyday landscapes and blighted areas. Through its ground-breaking approach and its broader scope, it complements the Council of Europe’s and UNESCO’s heritage conventions.</p>
<u>European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)</u>	<p>The ERDF (Regulation UE 2021/1058) is designed to strengthen economic, social and territorial cohesion in the EU. The ERDF finances programmes in shared responsibility between the EC and national and regional authorities in MSs, whose administrations choose which projects to finance and take responsibility for day-to-day management. In the 2021-2027 period, the ERDF will enable investments to make Europe and its regions: more competitive and smarter, through innovation and support to small and medium-sized businesses, as well as digitisation and digital connectivity; greener, low-carbon and resilient; more connected by enhancing mobility; more social, by supporting employment, education, skills, social inclusion, equal access to healthcare, culture and sustainable tourism; closer to citizens, supporting locally-led development and sustainable urban development. The Reg. UE 2021/1058 explicitly mentions investments aimed at preventing soil pollution, but several soil threats could be addressed by the ERDF.</p>
<u>European Social Fund Plus (ESF+)</u>	<p>The new ESF+ (Regulation (EU) 2021/1057) is the EU’s main financial instrument for implementing the European Pillar of Social Rights, to support jobs and create a fair and socially inclusive society. In 2021-2027, the ESF+ will continue to provide an important contribution to the EU’s employment, social, education and skills policies, including</p>

	structural reforms in these areas. Soil-related topics can potentially be integrated in projects funded under EFS.
<u>European Territorial Cooperation - Interreg</u>	Interreg is the EU's instrument to support cooperation across regions and countries in and outside the EU. In 2021-2027, according to the Regulation (EU) 2021/1059, the ERDF and external financing instruments will continue to support cross-border mobility, environmental protection, emergency services, skilled jobs and access to public services. The regulation encompasses: cross-border cooperation along all EU land and maritime borders; transnational cooperation, including macro-regional strategies and sea basins; interregional cooperation, which builds networks and lets leading regions share their successes and experience with other territories. In addition, there are Interreg projects beyond EU borders cover several areas in the world: Interreg NEXT, which involves Eastern and Southern Neighbourhood partner countries; Interreg Outermost Regions, which deepens relations between the EU's remote regions and their neighbourhoods; Interreg IPA, which fosters cooperation of MSs with Western Balkan countries and Türkiye.
<u>Farm to Fork Strategy (F2F)</u>	At the heart of the UE Green Deal, the "Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system" aims to accelerate our transition to a sustainable food system that should: have a neutral or positive environmental impact; help to mitigate climate change and adapt to its impacts reverse the loss of biodiversity; ensure food security, nutrition and public health, making sure that everyone has access to sufficient, safe, nutritious, sustainable food; preserve affordability of food while generating fairer economic returns, fostering competitiveness of the EU supply sector and promoting fair trade. This means, inter alia, ensuring that the food chain, covering food production, transport, distribution, marketing and consumption, has a neutral or positive environmental impact, preserving and restoring the land, freshwater and sea-based resources on which the food system depends; helping to mitigate climate change and adapting to its impacts; protecting land, soil, water, air, plant and animal health and welfare; and reversing the loss of biodiversity; The strategy sets out both regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives, with the CAP and fisheries policies as key tools to support a just transition.
<u>Fertiliser Regulation</u>	The Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 opens the EU single market for fertilising products which previously had not been covered by harmonisation rules, such as organic and organo-mineral fertilisers, soil improvers, inhibitors, plant biostimulants or growing media. It lays down common rules on safety, quality and labelling requirements for fertilising products. It introduces limits for toxic contaminants for the first time in order to guarantee a high level of soil protection and reduces health and environmental risks, while allowing producers to adapt their manufacturing process to comply with the new limits. It maintains optional harmonisation, as it does not prevent non-harmonised fertilising products from being made available on the internal market in accordance with national law and the general free-movement rules. The latest consolidated version of the regulation incorporates five amendments adopted by the EC by means of delegated acts. Many MSs have set up national rules and standards for fertilisers which include more detailed environmental requirements than the Fertiliser Regulation.
<u>Fit for 55 package</u>	According to the Communication COM/2021/550 final, the Fit for 55 package is a set of proposals to revise and update EU legislation in line with the EU's 2030 Climate Target on the way to climate neutrality. This by reducing the EU's carbon footprint. The EU's climate objectives are: to ensure a just and socially fair transition; to maintain and strengthens innovation and competitiveness of EU industry while ensuring a level playing field vis-à-vis third country economic operators; to underpin the EU's position as leading the way in the global fight against climate change
<u>Floods Directive (FD)</u>	The FD (2007/60/EC) aims to reduce and manage the risks that floods pose to human health, the environment, cultural heritage and economic activity. It requires MSs to identify flood risk areas, map them and establish flood risk management plans. The FD foresees 6-yearly cycles aiming to reduce the risk of flood damage in the EU (that covering the period 2022-2027 is the third cycle). It does not explicitly address soil protection. However, some of measures that reduce the risk of flooding can contribute to soil protection, in particular measures that increase water infiltration and retention capacities of soils. For example, the FD may lead to the promotion of green infrastructure and land use planning rules to control run-off and pluvial flooding. This, in turn, can reduce soil sealing. The directive implementation can also promote

	<p>protection of soils by preventing the urbanisation of floodplain and riparian land. Since the measures are not mandatory, actual beneficial impacts on soils depend on interest and the willingness of competent authorities to implement measures beneficial for soils. The FD is in fact closely coordinated with the Water Framework Directive, in particular with flood risk management plans, river basin management plans, and public participation procedures.</p>
<p><u>Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action</u></p>	<p>This Regulation sets out the necessary legislative foundation for reliable, inclusive, cost-efficient, transparent and predictable governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action (governance mechanism), which ensures the achievement of the 2030 and long-term objectives and targets of the Energy Union in line with the 2015 Paris Agreement on climate change following the 21st Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (the ‘Paris Agreement’), through complementary, coherent and ambitious efforts by the Union and its Member States, while limiting administrative complexity.</p>
<p><u>Groundwater Directive (GWD)</u></p>	<p>The GWD (2006/118/EC) sets groundwater quality standards and introduces measures to prevent or limit inputs of pollutants into groundwater. It responds to the requirements of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) regarding the assessment of chemical status of pollutants in groundwater. It takes into account local characteristics and regional conditions and requires pollution trend studies and monitoring data. With operational measures to prevent or limit inputs of pollutants into groundwater, it complements the environmental objectives outlined in the WFD. Agricultural activities, in particular the application of nitrogen and pesticides on fields, contribute to pollutant concentrations in groundwater and need to be addressed to meet the objectives of the Directive. This implies also soil management practices which reduce the need for nitrogen and pesticide application.</p>
<p><u>Habitats and Birds Directives</u></p>	<p>The two Directives form the cornerstones of EU biodiversity policy. Together, the two directives have also created the Natura 2000 Network – which is now the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world. The overall objective of the Birds Directive (79/409/EEC) and the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) is to ensure that the species and habitat types they protect are maintained, or restored, to a favourable conservation status throughout their natural range within the EU. The directives do not state any direct relevance to soil protection; however, the conservation measures which must be put into place for terrestrial ecosystems may involve actions which positively impact on soil. For example, soils benefit from measures that reduce the intensity of farming. In particular, reduced areas of monoculture, reduced input of chemical fertilisers and plant protection products contribute positively to soil biodiversity and soil organic matter, and may reduce erosion, contamination and compaction. In addition, the Birds Directive promotes the protection of wetlands, which might contribute to the increased size of areas with high soil organic matter content. Furthermore, it aims to reduce the pollution of habitats, which in turn might reduce soil contamination. More generally, the establishment of conservation areas required in both directives may reduce land degradation.</p>
<p><u>Horizon Europe</u></p>	<p>The Horizon Europe is the 9th EU’s Framework Programme for Research and Innovation in force until 2027. Its legal basis is represented by the Council Decision (EU) 2021/764. It tackles climate change, helps to achieve the UN’s SDGs and boosts the EU’s competitiveness and growth. The programme facilitates collaboration and strengthens the impact of research and innovation in developing, supporting and implementing EU policies while tackling global challenges. For this purpose, it incorporates five missions: Adaptation to climate change; Cancer; Oceans and waters; Climate-neutral and smart cities; a Soil Deal for Europe. The main goal of this latter is to establish 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. Its 8 objectives are: to reduce desertification; to conserve soil organic carbon stocks; to stop soil sealing and increase re-use of urban soils; to reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration; to prevent erosion; to improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity; to reduce the EU global footprint on soils; and to improve soil literacy in society. In addition, soil issue can be addressed by mean the innovation and research activities within the cluster 6 “Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment”. Finally, the European Partnerships with EU and associated countries, the private sector, foundations and other stakeholders aim at addressing some of the most pressing challenges through concerted R&I initiatives.</p>

<u>Industrial Emissions Directive (IED)</u>	<p>The Directive 2010/75/EU aims to prevent pollution or at least reduce emissions to air, water, and land and to prevent the generation of waste in order to reduce the environmental impacts from industrial activities. In 2022, the Commission adopted proposals to revise the IED by increasing the focus on energy, water and material efficiency and reuse, in addition to promoting the use of safer, less toxic or non-toxic chemicals in industrial processes. The directive directly addresses soil protection. In its current version the IED requires that industrial installations operate in accordance with permits, which includes environmental protection obligations. In case an installation's activity involves the use, production or release of a hazardous substance which may lead to contamination of soil or groundwater, a baseline report is required. The report assesses the state of soil contamination prior to operation of the installation. The re-assessment following cessation of activities is expected to identify any changes in the level of soil contamination. Where significant pollution of soil has been caused, the operation must take the necessary measures (taking into account technical feasibility) to return the site to the state it was. Contamination is also indirectly targeted by the requirements for waste incineration and co-incineration plant sites to avoid unauthorised and accidental releases to soil, and to take the necessary precautions in the delivery and reception of waste to prevent or limit the amount of pollution to soil.</p>
<u>INSPIRE Directive</u>	<p>The Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE) Directive - Directive 2007/2/EC - lays down general rules setting up an infrastructure for spatial information for the purposes of the EU environmental policies and for policies or activities which may have an impact on the environment. The Directive places requirements on public bodies that produce, receive, manage or update spatial datasets that cover all of the land and marine areas over which the State has to create such EU-related spatial data infrastructure. This European spatial data infrastructure will: enable public sector organisations to share environmental spatial information; facilitate public access to spatial information across Europe; assist in policy-making across boundaries. INSPIRE is based on the infrastructures for spatial information established and operated by EU SMs</p>
<u>IPARD III</u>	<p>The Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA) includes support for IPA Rural Development programmes (IPARD III in the 2021-27 period) in order to provide the beneficiary countries with concrete financial and technical help to achieve a balanced territorial development by raising social, environmental and economic standards in rural areas. This with the aims to: strengthen the competitiveness and viability of the agri-food sectors by building an agriculture capable of competing with market forces, ensure sustainable management of natural resources, and increase resilience to climate change. The countries currently benefitting from IPARD III support are: Albania, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Türkiye.</p>
<u>Landfill Directive</u>	<p>The Landfill Directive (99/31/EC) aims to prevent or reduce the negative effects of landfilling of waste on the environment during the whole life-cycle of the landfill. In particular, it addresses the pollution of surface water, groundwater, soil and air, and effects on the global environment as well as risks to human health. The directive directly addresses soil contamination. It sets operational and technical requirements to prevent leachate infiltration into the soil (e.g., regarding the location and design of the landfill, permeability and thickness requirements for the landfill's base and sides). Furthermore, the directive considers landfilling as the least preferable option which should be limited to the minimum and sets targets to reduce the total amount of biodegradable municipal waste. Thereby it indirectly contributes to reducing soil contamination and soil sealing (in regard to land covered by landfills). In addition, this has a general positive effect on soil health and quality and thus enhances soil biodiversity.</p>

<u>LIFE Programme</u>	<p>The LIFE programme (Regulation UE 2021/783) is the EU's funding instrument for environment and climate action. It aims to co-finance projects which contribute to the implementation, updating and development of EU environmental and climate policy and legislation. The general objective is to contribute to the shift towards a sustainable, circular, energy-efficient, renewable energy-based, climate-neutral and resilient economy, in order to protect, restore and improve the quality of the environment, including the air, water and soil, and to halt and reverse biodiversity loss and to tackle the degradation of ecosystems, including by supporting the implementation and management of the Natura 2000 network, thereby contributing to sustainable development. The LIFE Programme would support the demonstration of techniques, approaches and best practices that can be replicated and upscaled. Innovative solutions would contribute to the improvement of environmental performance and sustainability, in particular for the development of sustainable farming practices in the areas active in the fields of climate, water, soil, biodiversity and waste. There are synergies with other programmes and policies, such as the CAP and the EIP-Agri.</p>
<u>LULUCF Regulation</u>	<p>The land use sector encompasses the management of cropland, grassland, wetlands, forests, settlements and includes land use change such as afforestation (planting trees), deforestation, or draining of peatlands. Agricultural and forest lands alone cover more than three-quarters of the EU's territory, providing ample opportunity to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere and combat climate change. The Regulation (UE) 841/2018 on the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions and removals from land use, land use change and forestry in the 2030 climate and energy framework, and amending Regulation (EU) No 525/2013 and Decision No 529/2013/EU sets out the commitments of MSs for the LULUCF sector that contribute to achieving the objectives of the Paris Agreement and meeting the greenhouse gas emission reduction target of the Union for the period from 2021 to 2030. To help reach climate neutrality, for the first time, the revised LULUCF regulation has a separate land-based net carbon removals target of 310 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent by 2030. This EU-wide target is to be implemented through binding net removal national targets for the LULUCF sector. The Regulation lays down the rules for the accounting of emissions and removals from LULUCF.</p>
<u>National Emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants</u>	<p>In order to move towards achieving levels of air quality that do not give rise to significant negative impacts on and risks to human health and the environment, the Directive (UE) 2016/2284 on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants, amending Directive 2003/35/EC and repealing Directive 2001/81/EC, establishes the emission reduction commitments for the MS' anthropogenic atmospheric emissions of sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC), ammonia (NH₃) and fine particulate matter (PM 2.5). In addition, the Directive requires that national air pollution control programmes be drawn up, adopted and implemented.</p>
<u>Natural Restoration Law</u>	<p>On the 22nd June 2022 the EC adopted first-ever legislation that explicitly targets the restoration of Europe's nature, to repair the 80% of European habitats that are in poor condition, and to bring back nature to all ecosystems, from forest and agricultural land to marine, freshwater and urban ecosystems. Under the proposal for a Nature Restoration Law, legally binding targets for nature restoration in different ecosystems will apply to every MS, complementing existing laws. The aim is to cover at least 20% of the EU's land and sea areas by 2030 with nature restoration measures, and eventually extend these to all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050. Ecosystems with the greatest potential for removing and storing carbon and preventing or reducing the impact of natural disasters such as floods will be the top priorities. The new law builds on existing legislation but covers all ecosystems rather than being limited to the Habitats Directive and Natura 2000 protected areas, aiming to put all natural and semi-natural ecosystems on the path to recovery by 2030. The proposed targets include forest and agricultural ecosystems, overall increase of biodiversity, and a positive trend for grassland butterflies, farmland birds, drained peatlands under agricultural use and peat extraction sites. EU MSs are expected to submit National Restoration Plans to the Commission within two years of the Regulation coming into force.</p>

<u>Nitrates Directive</u>	<p>The EU Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) aims to protect surface waters and groundwater against pollution by nitrates from agricultural sources. It requires that MSs to identify Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZ) and set up action plans for these zones. MSs must draw up a code of good agricultural practices, which farmers apply on a voluntary basis. The directive implies the use of soil management measures to reach its aim. Such measures include, among others, the use of cover crops or crop rotations, appropriate fertilisation balanced according to timing, crop needs, climate, etc.; and restrictions on application periods or levels of fertiliser in the NVZ. This can reduce traffic as well as stocking rates and therefore decrease the risk of soil compaction. Reducing the use of fertiliser can also reduce diffuse soil contamination.</p>
<u>Pesticides Directive</u>	<p>The Directive 2009/128/EC aims to achieve a sustainable use of pesticides and to reduce risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment. Member States are required to establish National Action Plans which include quantitative objectives and measures to reduce the risks of pesticides. The Directive promotes the use of integrated pest management and alternative approaches or techniques such as non-chemical alternatives to pesticides. The Directive does not explicitly address soil protection. However, soils benefit from the reduced amount of pesticides applied on plants and consequently reaching the soil, thus reducing the risk of soil contamination. Furthermore, lower amounts of pesticides reduce the negative impact on microbial activity in soil, which enhances both soil biodiversity and soil organic matter content. The Directive also promotes the establishment of buffer and safeguard zones and the planting of hedges along surface waters to reduce exposure of water bodies to spray drift of pesticides, drain flow and run-off. This reduces soil erosion from the banks of water bodies.</p>
<u>Renewable Energy Directive (REDII)</u>	<p>The Directive (EU) 2018/2001 is a recast of the Directive 2009/28/EC (REDI) as part of the ‘Clean energy for all Europeans package’. It establishes a common framework for the promotion of energy from renewable sources in the EU and sets a binding target of 32% for the overall share of energy from renewable sources in the EU’s gross final consumption of energy in 2030. It also establishes sustainability and greenhouse gas emissions saving criteria for biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels and lays down rules on financial support to enhance the use of renewable energy usage. For instance, those produced from waste and residues derived not from forestry but from agricultural land shall be taken into account for the purposes of the Directive only where operators or national authorities have monitoring or management plans in place in order to address the impacts on soil quality and soil carbon.</p>
<u>Sewage Sludge Directive (SSD)</u>	<p>The SSD 86/278/EEC encourages the correct use of sewage sludge in agriculture and to regulate its use in order to prevent harmful effects on soil, vegetation, animals and humans. The principal benefit of the SSD is its role in the protection of human health and the environment against the harmful effects of contaminated sludge in agriculture. To this end, it prohibits the use of untreated sludge on agricultural land unless it is injected or incorporated into the soil. The SSD also requires that sludge be used in such a way that account is taken of the nutrient requirements of plants and that the quality of the soil and of surface and groundwater is not impaired.</p>
<u>EU Soil Strategy for 2030</u>	<p>Healthy soils are essential for achieving climate neutrality, a clean and circular economy and stopping desertification and land degradation. They are also essential to reverse biodiversity loss, provide healthy food and safeguard human health. The update of the 2006 Soil Thematic Strategy, i.e. the EU Soil strategy for 2030 “Reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate” - COM/2021/699 final - provides the framework and concrete steps towards protecting and restoring soils and ensuring that they are used sustainably. As part of this, a new Soil Monitoring Law has been proposed to ensure a level playing field and a high level of environmental and health protection. Moreover, the Strategy is a key deliverable of the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 and will contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal.</p>
<u>Soil Monitoring Law</u>	<p>On 5th July 2023, the EU proposed a new Soil Monitoring Law to protect and restore soils and ensure their sustainable use. It provides a legal framework to help achieve healthy soils by 2050, i.e. to address key soil threats, such as erosion, floods and landslides, loss of soil organic matter, salinisation, contamination, compaction, sealing, as well as loss of soil biodiversity. This will be done through a robust and coherent monitoring framework for all soils across the EU, so that MSs can take measures to regenerate degraded soils making sustainable soil management the norm in the EU. It</p>

	requires MSs to identify potentially contaminated sites, investigate these sites and address unacceptable risks for human health and the environment, thereby contributing to a toxic-free environment by 2050.
<u>Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive</u>	The Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive (2001/42/EC) aims to reduce environmental impacts from plans and programmes, including negative impacts on soil, by requiring an assessment of the likely significant effects prior to adoption of the plans and programmes. The directive particularly targets the following sectors: agriculture, forestry, fisheries, energy, industry, transport, waste and water management, telecommunications, tourism, town and country planning as well as land use. For plans and programmes that are expected to have significant effects, an environmental report has to be prepared describing these effects and including reasonable alternatives. This report must contain information about the likely significant effects on soil, which could touch upon multiple different soil threats – such as erosion, contamination, salinisation, loss of biodiversity, loss of soil organic matter, soil sealing. All of the information contained in the report and public consultations have to be considered before adopting the respective plan or programme.
<u>Sustainable bioeconomy for Europe</u>	The update of 2012 European Bioeconomy Strategy proposes actions to scale-up and deploy locally the bioeconomy, capitalising on and going beyond the previous successful R&I investments, in order to create growth and job opportunities at local level, to reinforce the bio-based sector and contribute to the modernisation of EU industry, to protect the environment and enhance ecosystems' functions and biodiversity.
<u>United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD)</u>	The UNCCD was established in 1994 to protect and restore our land and ensure a safer, just, and more sustainable future. The UNCCD is the only legally binding framework set up to address desertification and the effects of drought. The Convention – based on the principles of participation, partnership and decentralization – is a multilateral commitment to mitigate the impact of land degradation, and protect our land so we can provide food, water, shelter and economic opportunity to all people. There are 197 Parties to the Convention, including 196 country Parties (among them Latvia, Italy, Spain, and Türkiye) and the EU.
<u>Waste Management Extractive Industries Directive</u>	The Directive 2006/21/EC on the management of waste from extractive industries and amending Directive 2004/35/EC provides for measures, procedures and guidance to prevent or reduce as far as possible any adverse effects on the environment, in particular water, air, soil, fauna and flora and landscape, and any resultant risks to human health, brought about as a result of the management of waste from the extractive industries.
<u>Water Framework Directive (WFD)</u>	The Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC) establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters and groundwater. The key objectives of the WFD are set out in Article 4 of the Directive. It requires Member States to use their River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs) and Programmes of Measures (PoMs) to protect and, where necessary, restore water bodies in order to reach good status, and to prevent deterioration. Good status means both good chemical and good ecological status. The WFD does not explicitly address soil protection. However, in addressing water quality and quantity objectives, the Directive addresses agricultural pressures contributing which are associated with soil threats. For example, nutrient runoff is strongly linked to soil erosion, pesticide loads are linked to diffuse soil contamination (e.g. with pesticides) and loss of soil biodiversity, water abstraction in coastal areas is linked to soil salinisation. Achieving the WFD objectives also requires the implementation of soil management measures which contribute to soil protection, such as measures reducing soil erosion and compaction, restoration of wetlands, or reduced abstraction of groundwater in certain areas. On the 26 th October 2022, the EU Commission released its proposal for modifying three important water management Directives: the WFD (Directive 2000/60), the GWD (Directive 2006/118/EC), and the Directive on Environmental Quality Standards (EQSD, Directive 2008/105/EC). The proposed amendments and changes address inadequacies identified in the previous water legislation.

<u>Zero Pollution Action Plan</u>	On 12 th May 2021, the European Commission adopted the EU Action Plan: “Towards a Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil” (COM/2021/400 final), which is a key deliverable of the European Green Deal. The zero pollution vision for 2050 is for air, water and soil pollution to be reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems, that respect the boundaries with which our planet can cope, thereby creating a toxic-free environment.
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1.3 Agroecology for agricultural soil health

As highlighted in the previous paragraph, UE policy framework and national policies for agricultural soil represent a complex policy landscape made up of policy strategies, targets and instruments, very fragmented, and affected by multiple visions and goals across different policy domains and levels of governance. An effective representation of such complexity is provided by Figure 1, which is adapted from the review by Domenech and Bahn-Walkowiak (2018) on the policy frameworks of the EU and SMs for resource efficiency and the circular economy.

Fig. 1 - The general framework of the UE Soil-based Policies

Source: Our adaptation on Domenech and Bahn-Walkowiak (2019).

In this context, integrating the agroecological principles into the conversation around agricultural soil health would allow building a long-term vision for the future of farming more responsive to multiple environmental and social needs.

The term “Agroecology” was used for the first time in the scientific literature in the 1920s and 1930s by authors from Russia and the European Union (France, Germany and Italy) to designate the application of ecological methods and principles in agricultural sciences, including disciplines like biology, ecology, zoology, crop physiology, as well as agronomy from the first definition of “agroecosystem” given by Odum in 1969 (Gallardo-López et al., 2018; HLPE, 2019).

Over the past two decades, agroecology has increasingly been seen as a transdisciplinary, participatory and action-oriented approach based on three manifestations of science, a set of practices

and a social movement, which are seen as interdependent and fundamental to a holistic ecological approach to food systems (Wezel et al., 2009; Loconto and Fouilleux, 2019; Wezel et al., 2020). This agroecological approach has also evolved by incorporating a critical engagement with the prevalent political-economic structures and asymmetrical power relations affecting food systems (Méndez et al., 2013).

Figure 2 shows the historical evolution of agroecology and its principles, where picture a) represents the disciplinary basis of the agroecological principles; picture b) represents the scales i.e. how agroecology has expanded from the field, farm and agroecosystem scale to encompass the whole food system; the picture c) represents the three manifestations mentioned above, plus a fourth represented by policies and laws. Today agroecology includes all the ecological, socio-cultural, technological, economic and political dimensions of food systems, from production to consumption.

This is in line with the position of the association Agroecology Europe (2017), according to which agroecology “encompasses the whole food system from the soil to the organisation of human societies. It is value-laden and based on core principles”.

Since agroecology encompasses a range of principles that vary in both scale and timeframe, a very important contribution to the development of the concept of agroecology was given by Gliessman (2016), who described agroecology as “a way of redesigning food systems, from the farm to the table, with a goal of achieving ecological, economic, and social sustainability”. He also proposed a framework to classify the changes in the food system into 5 levels (6 if conventional agriculture is associated with level 0).

The first three levels describe the steps which farmers can actually take on their farms to convert from industrial or conventional agroecosystems (Figure 2). The first two levels are incremental, while the real transformative change towards sustainability occurs at levels 3, 4 and 5, moving from the scale of landscape or water catchment areas to communities in food systems and society.

At Level 1, which is that of a mature of food systems, a first step towards sustainability is the search for greater efficiency, i.e. more product with fewer inputs (physical, energy) and with a reduction in the use of some inputs, especially those which are expensive, scarce, or critical in terms of the potential environmental damage that they generate.

The next step, Level 2, is that of replacing the inputs with the more conventional ones of fossil rather than renewable energy, the use of inputs of biological origin rather than synthetic ones, which in some way make it possible to define more environmentally friendly practices.

Level 3 is the one that aims to redesign the agroecosystem by considering its components and the interactions that these components can have, and, which reads the agroecosystem in terms of ecological processes and which also aims to increase the diversification of the systems and to enhance the relationships that exist between the different components within the system but to make it more stable, more resilient, and therefore functionally more effective.

The level 4 takes into consideration the fact that food systems are still being transformed by attempting a reconnection between citizens, consumers, on one side, and food producers, farmers, on the other, in other words the two group of actors who have been greatly distanced due to traditional agricultural models.

With Level 5, change is global in scope and reaches beyond the food system to the nature of human culture, civilization, progress, and development; agroecology provides ways to build upon farm-scale and farmer-driven change processes to a full re-thinking of how humans relate to each other and to the earth, and what it really means to live sustainably. The important role of food systems in

mitigating and adapting to climate change as a global issue is an example of the value of Level 5 (Gliessman, 2016).

Fig. 2 - Historical evolution of agroecology and its principles

Source: Wezel et al., 2020.

Figure 3 also introduces two other important frameworks: the comprehensive set of 13 agroecological principles contributing to FSN, which was consolidated by the international High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition (HLPE) in July 2019, and the 10 elements of agroecology identified by the FAO (2018) in order to guide policymakers, practitioners and other stakeholders in planning, managing and evaluating agroecological transitions to “transform their food and agricultural systems, to mainstream sustainable agriculture on a large scale, and to achieve Zero Hunger and multiple other SDGs”.

Fig. 3 – HLPE principles and FAO elements of agroecology arranged by 5 AT levels

Source: our adaptation from Gliessman (2016) and Agroecology Info Pool (<https://www.agroecology-pool.org/13aeprinciples/>).

It is worth noting that one of the 13 principles is addressed to soil health, i.e. to “secure and enhance soil health and functioning for improved plant growth, particularly by managing organic matter and by enhancing soil biological activity”. Although directly applied to the farm scale, this principle has important links with some FAO elements (FAO, 2018; Wezel et al., 2020):

- “synergies”, which leads to “enhances key functions across food systems, supporting production and multiple ecosystem services (animals, crops, trees, soil and water)”, for instance, by improving soil structure and fertility or controlling soil erosion using plants;
- “diversity”, since diversification, including for example agroforestry, contour farming and cover cropping, is “key to agroecological transitions to ensure food security and nutrition while conserving, protecting and enhancing natural resources”;
- “resilience”, because “enhanced resilience of people, communities and ecosystems is key to sustainable food and agricultural systems”.

The concept of diversification has been recently explained within some research projects. In particular, the University of Wageningen’s work has described crop arrangements in terms of spatial, temporal, and genetic diversification. This approach highlights the complexity of the system and the various possibilities for diversification that can be implemented simultaneously to design effective ecosystems or business systems (Ditzler et al., 2021).

The All-Organic project (Agroecology Living Labs within the CORE Organic Coordination co-funded within Horizon 2020), which aims to promote the diversification of biological systems functioning according to the principles of agroecology, also takes into account the diversification of practices (Figure 4).

This means emphasising different working methods and soil fertility management. All of the aspects of diversification should be considered simultaneously in the planning and management of an agroecological system.

Today, agroecology is gaining attention as a way to achieve some of the Sustainable Development Goals as defined by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (Millennium Institute, 2018; HLPE, 2019; Swiss National FAO Committee, 2019. In particular, agroecology can contribute to no poverty (SDG 1), zero hunger (SDG 2), good health and well-being (SDG 3), decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), responsible consumption and production (SDG 12), climate action (SDG 13) and life on land (SDG 15) (Figure 5). Motarjemi et al. (2023) attribute this great potential of agroecology to “its holistic approach towards the challenges facing the global food system”.

However, in the particular case of soil health the scaling up of agroecology is hindered by a number of limitations and barriers, some of which have been identified in scientific literature (Swiss National FAO Committee, 2019) and are outlined below:

- there is a time lag between the implementation of agroecological principles and the resulting benefits, such as soil fertility improvements and yield increases;
- the outcomes of a number of agroecological practices depend on collective action at the landscape scale, involving multiple farms and a range of actors. This requires higher levels of coordination and increases transaction costs;
- being more diverse, agroecological systems tend to produce a greater number of crop or livestock products, but in smaller quantities of each, which limits market and processing opportunities. These systems require higher transaction costs, high levels of knowledge and risk-taking/experimentation;
- there is a mismatch between knowledge and advisory systems needed to support agroecology and build the capacity of actors. There is also a lack of long-term inter- and transdisciplinary research on agroecology which takes into account the context specificity. This limits research in the field and thus the evidence base that can be used to inform legislation and policy-making;
- agroecology for healthy soils requires different types of government policy instruments (e.g. subsidies or grants, mandatory or voluntary). There is a need to better understand which government policies can support it and sustainable agriculture in general.

Fig. 4 – The ALL-Organic project

ALL-Organic

The ALL-Organic research project will promote a functional network of experiences, models, and systems able to support the development of diversified organic food systems, with the aim of implementing robust and resilient organic crop productions, by involving food system actors from field to fork.

The integration of agroecological approach with the enhancement of functional agro-biodiversity in organic farming systems is seen as a key lever for the development of sustainable, robust and resilient agriculture productions. This requires transformative changes based on the redesign of the organic agroecosystems to increase their spatial, temporal and genetic diversification in order to amplify ecosystem services. But more knowledge on the relations among diversification components and their agro-environmental and socio-economic performances is needed to support system redesign.

Aim

The project aims to demonstrate the environmental and socio-economic quality performances of diversified agroecologically centered organic farming systems, confirming their pivotal role in the transformative pathways for transformation of food systems towards sustainability and to catalyze consumers awareness on the overall advantages of diversified system based organic food and produce evidence-based recommendations targeting different socio-economic group at national, transnational and European level.

Coordinator & Partners

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Source: <https://projects.au.dk/coreorganiccofund/2021-call-projects/all-organic>.

Fig. 5 – Agroecology to reach the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Source: United Nations (UNDP).

1.4 Agroecology and policies

The literature suggests that there exists a reciprocal relationship between agroecology and policy. According to the FAO⁸, “agroecology represents an overarching and comprehensive systems framework to guide public policies towards sustainable agriculture and food systems”. By fostering integrated and inter-ministerial policy design and implementation, and by favouring a responsible and transparent governance of resources through the active engagement of multiple stakeholders, agroecological transitions can support the simultaneous achievement of multiple sustainability objectives. Conversely, as pointed out by Baatz and Finger (2023), because agroecology aims to reduce the negative external effects of conventional agricultural practices, contribute to the provision of ecosystem services, and enhance biodiversity, existing policies, even if not explicitly mentioned, can encourage farmers to adopt agroecological practices. According to the two authors, “policies to support agroecology can range from being producer-oriented, consumer-oriented, and market-/trade-oriented, or they may be oriented toward creating an enabling environment representing cross-cutting approaches”. Rural community-oriented policies are also growing in the European agricultural policy landscape.

Before going into detail, it should be recalled that the EU has mentioned agroecology and its principles and criteria in five key strategic documents: the European Green Deal 2019, the Circular Economy Action Plan 2020, the Farm to Fork Strategy 2020, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the Organic Agriculture Action Plan 2021. Specifically, agroecology is explicitly mentioned in the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy as a possible pathway towards sustainable agri-food systems. The relevance of agroecology and how it should contribute to sustainability were considered during the debate which accompanied the definition of the CAP 2023-2027, when it was suggested giving more room to agroecology (e.g. within eco-schemes and the Strategic National Programs of MSs). However, a cursory evaluation of the current CAP 2023-2027 shows that

⁸ This quote is taken from the following website: <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/overview/en/>. It should be noted that from the same page it is possible access the repository *AgroecologyLex*, which specialises in the different legal frameworks, policies and programmes related to agroecology in different countries at world level.

agroecology is not widely implemented. Apart from a few cases, such as the French Strategic CAP Plan, conservative forces have prevented agroecology from playing a more significant role in the CAP 2023-2027. The current CAP interventions can be seen as levers of transition towards agroecology, from an agroecological perspective, but how agriculture and food systems can contribute to addressing sustainability challenges is still highly controversial.

One of the many positions expressed (DeSIRA Partnership for Innovation, 2021), which does not represent an official position of the EC, remains stuck in the continuum (with many overlaps) observed between the two main transition pathways in question: The first pathway is based on “a sustainable intensification of agricultural systems” and is based on concepts such as climate-smart agriculture or precision agriculture, as well as incremental innovation by using new technologies. The second pathway is based on agroecological approaches and aims to design agroecosystems while preserving the regenerative capacity of natural resources.

On the other hand, the European research programs and projects are pointing towards agroecology to build a comprehensive framework of transformative knowledge to be transferred to policies, communities, and multi-level governance systems. The primary aim is to ensure that agroecology is better understood and implemented.

The interest in the European agroecological research policy was explored by Iocola et al. (2022) as part of the activities of the Project “Agroecology for Europe” (AE4EU)⁹. With the aim to identify research projects involved in agroecology starting from 2014, this mapping was performed by consulting the main relevant available databases on to three different categories of funded projects: a) EU research projects financed by research programs framed and funded by EU (i.e., within the framework of Horizon 2020); b) transnational research projects financed by research programs co-framed and co-funded by MSs with the participation of the EU (i.e., ERA-NETs within the past Horizon framework and European Partnerships of Horizon Europe). The resulting database¹⁰ includes 68 European projects, 56 transnational projects, and 300 national projects, with a total of 1,315 participants (public or private research institutions, organizations, and enterprises involved as partners).

Today agroecology is explicitly mentioned within both the Horizon Europe 2021-2027 and the new co-funded European R&I Partnership “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures”, otherwise known as “Agroecology Partnership”, which is envisaged to officially start in January 2024. The partnership aims to promote a European large-scale endeavour for an agricultural sector that is fit to meet the targets and challenges in relation to climate change, biodiversity loss, food security and sovereignty and the environment, while ensuring a profitable and attractive activity for farmers. It has been developed upon the mandate of the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) through its Strategic Working Group on Agroecology (SCAR-AE). In line with its Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), the Partnership will conduct institutional research to strengthen the implementation of agroecology in Europe.

⁹ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/>

¹⁰ The file, in Excel format, is published at the website: <https://zenodo.org/records/7248937>.

2. METHODOLOGY

This section briefly describes the methodology used to carry out the investigation of the policies addressing soil issues in the UE and task reference countries. The method is based on desk research guided by the ad hoc protocol in Annex I and developed according to an analytical framework based on five main policy areas. The desk research was carried out by one or more representatives from each of the 7 participating countries. A general description of the analytical framework of investigation and the method used to summarise the results is provided below.

2.1 The analytical framework

In table 2 we provide an indicative, although not exhaustive, classification of policy instruments into five main policy areas which could contribute to addressing the management of agricultural soil in the EU and Türkiye according to the agroecological principle of soil health (see paragraph 1.3). These policy areas are: Incentivising the adoption of sustainable practices; Enabling participatory processes for sustainable development; Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape; Co-creation and sharing of innovation and knowledge; Triggering new market opportunities.

The classification is an adaptation of the work of Gava et al. (2022), which investigates policies supporting the AT of food systems in the EU. The reference to AT is motivated by the fact that this process, more than other, brings into play the key role of public and private institutions and governance in influencing production choices (Lampkin et al., 2020; Peeters et al., 2021; Hansen-Kuhn, 2023) and, therefore, the sustainability of the management of natural resources, including agricultural soils.

Tab. 2 - A classification of the policy instruments contributing to the agroecological principle of soil health

Policy Areas	Description of the main policy instruments
Incentivising the adoption of sustainable practices	<i>Grants for the conservation and improvement of agricultural soils:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAP investments to purchase equipment for sustainable production methods
	<i>Aids for sustainable practices:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAP schemes for the climate, the environment and animal welfare (so called “eco-schemes”) • AEC measures within the CAP and IPARD
Enabling participatory processes for sustainable development	<i>Grants and aids</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Priority access to public support for collective actions • Other measures within the CAP and IPARD • LIFE programme projects
	<i>Legal empowerment</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acknowledgement of groups of actors or networks promoting environmental projects
Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape	<i>Rules for protected areas</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for the designation of protected areas and their management
	<i>Rules for vulnerable zones</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules to monitor and manage environmental pressures to safeguard soil

	<i>Landscape regulation</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rules aimed at protecting agricultural land from land take, soil sealing and landscape degradation
	<i>Conditionality</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirements and Standards for CAP payments
Co-creation and sharing of knowledge and innovation	<i>Knowledge and Innovation networks</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot projects by the Operational Groups of PEI – Agri Living Labs and Lighthouses under the Horizon Europe programme
	<i>Knowledge exchange and training</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farm advisory services and technical assistance Training, including coaching and exchange of best practices
Triggering new market opportunities	<i>Rules and funding for short food chain initiatives</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actions to promote green public procurement Actions to promote local farmer markets Educational campaigns
	<i>Rules for typical products</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production specifications within quality certification schemes
	<i>Voluntary certification schemes</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon credit schemes Organic and Quality products certifications

Source: Our adaptation on Gava et al. (2022).

Instruments belonging under the policy area ‘Incentives for the adoption of sustainable practices’ allow facing economic and financial barriers. Specifically, economic barriers arise in all those circumstances where implementation costs outweigh private benefits and there is no economic advantage for the farmer in implementing a change in farming practices. Such barriers are usually addressed in the form of area-based payments to compensate farmers for the additional costs and income foregone (as in the EU CAP eco-schemes and AEC measures, as well as in the Türkiye’s IPARD AEC measures). Financial barriers occur in all those circumstances where the implementation of the more sustainable practice requires up-front investment and, therefore, the availability of financial resources. Such barriers are usually addressed in the form of grants for investments. These instruments are designed in compliance with the EU regulations but are co-financed and implemented by MSs according to their national (or regional) priorities, whether they are under the Strategic Plan of the CAP 2023-2027 or, in the case of the Turkish Government, under the IPARD III Program.

In line with the programmatic framework of the aforementioned CAP Strategic Plans, it is assumed that the funding under this policy area will contribute to some EU specific objectives. This will be demonstrated by the estimation of result indicators corresponding to the medium-term effects of the interventions, as codified in Annex I of the Regulation EU 2021/2115 (Table 3).

Instruments belonging to the policy area ‘Enabling participatory processes for sustainable development’ allows facing several barriers (e.g. trade barriers or coordination barriers between local actors), depending on the nature of the participatory initiatives promoted. Generally, participatory processes are addressed by means of two main complementary instruments: grants and aids, and the legal empowerment of groups of actors or networks with certain common goals. Grants and aids are

provided by means of financial instruments (e.g. under the national Strategic Plan of the CAP 2023-2027, the Turkish IPARD program or the LIFE Program), which often provide priority access to collective actions addressing environmental soil-related issues (e.g., grants for the construction of reservoirs or other infrastructure to fight land erosion at the territorial scale). Legal empowerment occurs when a public authority enacts laws to recognise, regulate, and enables access to funding for collective bodies/organisations (e.g., Eco-regions or/and Bio districts, Land associations, Rural districts). Legal empowerment can influence the process of interaction and decision-making between the actors involved in collective problems (Lurie and Brekken, 2019; Murdoch, 2000).

Tab. 3 - Soil-related CAP Objectives and the corresponding result indicators

EU specific objective	Result indicators
To contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, including by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration, as well as to promote sustainable energy.	R.12 Adaptation to climate change: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments to improve adaptation to climate change. R.14 Carbon storage in soils and biomass: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments to reduce emissions or to maintain or enhance carbon storage (including permanent grassland, permanent crops with permanent green cover, agricultural land in wetland and peatland). R.17 Afforested land: Area supported for afforestation, agroforestry and restoration, including breakdowns.
To foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, including by reducing chemical dependency.	R.19 Improving and protecting soils: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments beneficial for soil management to improve soil quality and biota (such as reducing tillage, soil cover with crops, crop rotation included with leguminous crops). R.26 Investments related to natural resources: Share of farms benefitting from CAP productive and non-productive investment support related to care for the natural resources. R.28 Environmental or climate-related performance through knowledge and innovation: Number of persons benefitting from advice, training, knowledge exchange, or participating in European Innovation Partnership (EIP) operational groups supported by the CAP related to environmental or climate-related performance.
To contribute to halting and reversing biodiversity loss, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes.	R.34 Preserving landscape features: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees.

Source: Regulation (EU) 2121/2115.

The instruments of the policy area ‘Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape’ allow facing cultural barriers as they affect the way in which people influence the territory where they live. These instruments usually take the form of environmental regulations (at EU or national or regional level) aimed at protecting the environment and the landscape.

Some of them contribute to setting the new conditionality system, which “links full receipt of CAP support to the compliance of farmers and other beneficiaries with basic standards concerning the environment, climate change, public health, plant health and animal welfare”¹¹. In other words, the CAP only provides payments covering commitments which go beyond the relevant SMRs and GAECs. SMRs imply compliance with the Union law, including relevant Directives in force (nitrates, water, birds, sludge, animal welfare etc.), while the GAEC standards imply compliance with the minimum management rules for farmers and other beneficiaries set by MSs to ensure that all agricultural areas, including land which is no longer used for production purposes, are maintained in good agricultural and environmental condition¹². Soil (protection and quality) is an integral part of such a conditionality and appears indirectly in the SMRs and directly as a main issue in some GAEC standards (GAEC 5, 6 and 7). GAECs are complemented by other national laws that often play an important role in combating soil degradation by providing additional rules on landscape and land use. The policy area ‘Co-creation and sharing of knowledge and innovation’ allow facing knowledge barriers. The instruments under this policy area can be divided into three categories: aids for innovative pilot projects implemented by the GOs of the European network of PEI-Agri; aids for the provision of farm advisory services and technical assistance, as well as training, coaching and exchange of best practices; aids for the development and networking of living labs and lighthouses within the Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ under the Horizon Europe Program.

The potential of these instruments in accompanying the adoption of sustainable management practices is broadly recognised, as they contribute to improving intangible assets such as skills, knowledge, attitudes and relationships. Particularly, the collaborative process of co-creation of knowledge is increasingly gaining recognition within the science, practice, and movement of agroecology: it fosters participatory learning and development, which differs from passive knowledge sharing. In addition, “when engaged in knowledge co-creation, farmers are identified in a variety of contexts as innovators who inspire and lead bottom-up transitions within their communities” (Utter et al., 2021).

The policy area ‘Triggering new market opportunities’ allows it to face trade barriers. Farmers are often locked into contractual relationships that prevent them from adopting sustainable practices. These instruments usually take the form of EU, national and regional laws to protect and valorise traditional productions (e.g. production specifications for PDO or PGI products), facilitate the creation of local value chains and to strengthen local brands in the global market. Bottom-up initiatives, such as Green Public Procurement (GPP) addressing the consumption of organic and healthy food in schools or other institutions, the reduction/zeroing of the fees for school meals for poor families, the introduction of food education in school programs (Galli et al., 2020), can also contribute to the creation of market conditions favourable to the environment and the integration of the agroecological principles in the food system. Other key contractual instruments are voluntary certification schemes, which include feedstock and supply chains for bioenergy, but also for food,

¹¹ This quote comes from the recital 41 of the Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the CAP Strategic Plans.

¹² SMRs and GAECs standard are listed in the Annex III of the Regulation (EU) 2021/2115.

feed and biomaterials (Meyer, 2017; Ting et al., 2016), and more recently carbon farming (Criscuoli et al., 2023).

2.2 Data collection and analysis

The protocol for data collection includes references to some relevant databases and websites to facilitate the collection of information at the national level. Specifically, information on GAEC standards, eco-schemes and AEC measures was retrieved from the common website (European Commission, 2022) of the CAP National Strategic Plans (NSPs), while Information on current legislation and policies in Türkiye was collected by project partners. Information on OGs dealing with soil health issues was retrieved from the EIP-AGRI database (EIP-AGRI, 2022). Information on living labs was retrieved from the official European living lab website (ENoLL, 2023). Finally, information on the state of implementation of environmental laws at the country level was retrieved from the European Commission's website on infringements (European Commission, 2023). Descriptive statistics and qualitative analysis are combined to provide a comprehensive overview of the policies affecting soil health in the reference countries.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Incentivising the adoption of sustainable practices

Figure 6 provides the share of funds that each reference Country has programmed for the 2023-2027 CAP programming period and, in the case of Türkiye, for IPARD III to promote soil health issues, as well as investments and advisory services accompanying sustainable innovations.

Adaptation to climate change (R.12 in figure 6) and improving soil carbon storage (R.14 in figure 6) are particularly addressed in the funding policies of PL (yellow line in figure 6), LV (green line in figure 6) and CZ (grey line in figure 6) compared to the other reference countries and the EU average (black line in figure 6). The improvement of carbon storage in soil is also strongly addressed in LT (light blue in figure 6). Improving and protecting soils (R.19 in figure 6) is particularly addressed in the funding policies of IT (bright blue in figure 6) and TR (purple in figure 6). CZ's funding policy also distinguishes from the other countries with respect to promoting knowledge and innovation (R.28 in figure 6) and investments to climate adaptation (R.16 in figure 6), revealing the existence of a funding policy comprehensive of different instruments in addressing environmental issues.

Investments for preserving natural resources (R.26 in figure 6) and actions to preserving landscape features (R.34 in figure 6) are weakly supported by the funding policies of most of the reference countries compared to the EU Average.

Table 4 provides further details that help to qualify the differences in the funding strategies addressing soil health in the reference countries. The list of measures addressing soil health directly (i.e., soil and land use management) and indirectly (i.e., investments and advisory services) is provided in the row headings of the table, while the share of CAP/IPARD funds allocated to each measure and the share of additional national funds are the two indicators provided in the column headings of the table for each reference country and the EU average.

The allocation of funds for land use change, cooperation actions, and advisory services is below the EU average for all reference countries, while virtually no funds are allocated to crop diversification

and agroforestry. The afforestation of agricultural land is particularly addressed in LV (79.9% of total national funds), together with the maintenance of permanent crops, the management of non-productive areas and tillage management. Fertilization management is particularly addressed in PL (11.1% of total funds) and drainage management in IT. Crop rotations and the use of cover crops are particularly addressed in ES, followed by IT. Sustainable investments are particularly promoted in IT. Finally, organic farming is particularly addressed in LV, LT, and IT; concerning ES, it is higher than the European average, if the additional national funds are taken into account.

An integrated reading of the two pieces of information provided in figure 6 and table 4, respectively, highlights the greater focus on land use change strategies and grassland management in the eastern EU reference countries and the greater focus on soil management and crop management on arable land in the southern EU reference countries and in Türkiye.

A final issue to highlight here is the additional contribution provided at national level to achieve the CAP result target indicators. Additional contributions are particularly relevant in LT, where the national government provides extra contributions to improve both afforestation and forest management. Such additional contributions are often aimed at promoting projects of public interest, where no private co-financing is foreseen.

Fig. 6 - Share of funds (CAP 2023-2027 for the EU and IPARD III for Türkiye) allocated to the achievement of soil health results indicators, knowledge dissemination and sustainable investments for some EU countries and Türkiye

Source: our elaboration on AGRIDATA (2023).

Note: Vertices of the polygon – Results indicators: R.12; R.14; R.19; R.16; R.26; R.17; R.34; R.28. Countries: IT – Italy; ES – Spain; CZ – Czech Republic; PL – Poland; LT – Lithuania; LV – Latvia; TR – Turkey; EU AVG – EU Average.

Tab. 4 – Distribution of funds addressing soil conservation practices, investments in agricultural assets to enhance environmental sustainability, advisory services and cooperation actions. A - Share of funds addressing the measure/ Total funds (CAP funds for EU countries and IPARD for Turkey); B - Share of national funds addressing the measure/ Total funds addressing the measure. Values are reported in percentage (%)

Measure	Country															
	IT		ES		CZ		PL		LT		LV		TR		EU AVG	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
Wetland management	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Tillage management	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.8	0.0	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0
Soil management	0.7	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	5.7
Other measures	3.5	0.0	0.9	1.8	15.9	0.0	1.3	0.0	1.7	0.0	5.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	8.7	2.2
Organic farming	6.2	1.7	2.6	3.4	5.7	0.0	3.6	0.0	9.6	0.0	10.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.5	5.5
Management of non-productive areas	0.4	2.3	2.4	2.3	0.0	0.0	2.5	0.0	1.9	0.0	4.2	0.0	8.0	0.0	2.9	4.9
Maintenance of permanent crops	0.6	0.0	3.8	0.2	6.5	0.0	0.4	0.0	1.0	0.0	6.6	8.9	0.0	0.0	1.4	0.5
Land use change	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0
Sustainable investments	6.8	3.2	1.3	5.8	1.1	0.0	0.9	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.6	36.3	0.0	0.0	5.6	10.5
Forest management	0.6	1.5	0.2	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	2.9
Fertilization management	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0
Crop rotation	2.4	0.0	6.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.0	0.0	0.6	0.0
Crop diversification	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0
Cover crops	2.4	0.0	4.6	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.0
Cooperation actions	0.4	2.0	0.6	5.6	0.2	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.2	9.1	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	17.1
Breeding management	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.2
Agroforestry	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0
Afforestation of agricultural land	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.3	50.0	1.9	79.9	0.0	0.0	0.4	11.6
Advisory services	0.4	1.5	0.6	2.2	0.2	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.3	9.1	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	14.2

Source: our elaboration on AGRIDATA (2023).

3.2 Enabling participatory processes for sustainable development

Table 5 provides a list of initiatives promoted at both national and EU level which are representative of empowering local actors in addressing soil health and other environmental issues.

Such initiatives are particularly promoted in IT in the form of dedicated regulations to recognise the work performed by different organisations involved in land use planning and management, such as bio districts, food and rural districts and land associations. Unlike CAP/IPARD interventions, these legislative initiatives are not influenced by a financial programming period and are of longer duration. However, these policy instruments can contribute significantly to triggering bottom-up initiatives by empowering local actors with ad hoc funding for their own local development plans, which often include environmental and socio-economic public and private initiatives. This may help to explain the reason why investments in IT are supported to a greater extent than in the other countries involved in the study (see Table 4).

The other countries involved in the study have provided less evidence of the existence of such instruments. It is interesting to note that the forestry initiatives in LV, LT, CZ, and ES, are led by forest owners' associations belonging to large supranational networks which strengthen their ability to lobby.

Tab. 5 – National legislative initiatives empowering local actors in addressing soil health and other environmental issues

Country	Regulation references	Brief description in relation to soil health issues
IT	Sicilian Region - Regional Act no. 21 of 2021	Provisions on agroecology, protection of biodiversity and Sicilian agricultural products and technological innovation in agriculture. This Act aims at increasing the minimum level of health and environmental protection ensured by the national law, and therefore provides for: the protection of human health, the natural environment, the biodiversity, the ecosystems and agricultural activities; the fight against desertification, hydrogeological risk and fires; the protection of Sicilian agricultural products and all related production sectors; an agro-forestry-pastoral model conforming to the criteria of agroecology; an efficient control and verification service in the agri-food sector. What is more, the Act enhances the transition towards a development model consistent with the European Green new Deal and implements programmes and plans concerning rural development.
IT	Law on Organic Farming and institution of Bio districts n. 23, 9/03/2022	The law provides general rules to set up organic farming and Bio districts in Italy, but it delegates to the Regions the definition of the areas of jurisdiction of organic districts and their ability to access funds. Only a few Regions still have a regional law on organic districts. With regard to soil issues, bio districts provide production rules that are more stringent than the regulation on organic farming and offer market opportunities that facilitate the valorisation of goods produced according to the bio districts rules.
IT	Law on food districts n. 205, 27/12/2017	The law provides general rules to set up food districts in Italy (similar to those for industrial districts). The main goal of food districts, which are widely represented all throughout the country, is to strengthen market power by improving quality differentiation strategies. The impact on soil health is variable and difficult to assess.

IT	Legislative decree n. 228/01 on the modernisation of the agricultural sector	The legislative decree provides general rules to set up rural districts and other forms of association to promote agriculture and rural development. Rural districts operate only in a few regions and are characterised by the development of cross-sectoral projects, including agriculture. Sustainable farming practices are sometimes promoted through rural districts.
IT	Regional law n. 19, 01/08/22 (Valle d'Aosta) Regional law n. 21, 02/11/16 on land associations (Piedmont)	Few Italian Regions provide rules to set up land associations with the aim of consolidating landholding, thus favouring access to land to limit land abandonment in marginal areas. Regional laws have followed the spontaneous emergence of land associations and has demonstrated being effective in accompanying the creation of new governance mechanisms for the management of agricultural lands in marginal areas.
LV	Latvian Forest Owners' Association (European Landowners' Organisation, Confederation of European Forest Owners, International Forestry Alliance)	After the implementation of the land reform (1992-1997), half of the forests are privately owned, of which 50% are operated as family forestry firms. Latvia has approximately 135,000 privately owned forest properties. Private forests are mainly characterised by naturally regenerated stands, diverse in species composition, size, age and structure. The Latvian Forest Owners' Association, founded in 2005, is a non-governmental organisation, which unites large and small private forest property owners, companies and municipalities, and property holders, and provides them with information, education and exchange of experience.
LT	Forest and Land Owners Association of Lithuania (European Landowners' Organisation, Confederation of European Forest Owners)	Restitution and land reform have created a large number of private forest owners. Approximately 45% of the forest land is privately owned. The average size of a forest plot in Lithuania is 3.4 ha. In April 1993, the Forest and Land Owners Association of Lithuania was founded to represent the interests of forest owners and to develop the institutional framework for the family forestry. Subsequently, it was registered as a public organisation (on 8 th June 1993). With the status of an independent public NGO, it is therefore recognised national organisation in Lithuania and internationally.
CZ	Association of Municipal and Private Forest Owners (Confederation of European Forest Owners)	The Association of Municipal and Private Forest Owners in the Czech Republic is a voluntary organisation which defends the common interests of non-state forest owners by associating communities of forest owners, corporate bodies established or formed by these subjects to manage their property, and by means of the association "Private Forests Chamber", also private forest owners. The main objectives of the Association are: participation in law-making, participation in the development of strategic documents and programmes, educational and advisory activities, international cooperation, joint timber trade, forest education.
ES	Confederation of Spanish Forest Owners Organizations (Confederation of European Forest Owners)	In 1987 the existing regional forest owners' associations founded their national confederation COSE (Confederación de Organizaciones de Selvicultores de España), in order to join the European forest owner's association, which assures the representation in Brussels.

Source: our elaboration on various references from research partners .

3.3 Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape

Tables 6-14 and table 15 provide respectively some information on the characteristics of the conditionality requirements in the form of GAECs and SMRs in each of the countries involved in the study. Each table follows the same structure, where we first provide a description of common requirements (i.e., similar commitments which are implemented in the countries), followed by a description of country-specific requirements (i.e., commitments that are required in given countries and not in others).

As might be expected, there are some key differences between TK and the other EU countries. This is merely because two different policy instruments are implemented in these areas, the CAP and the IPARD. Only GAEC 3 (Ban on burning arable stubble) and GAEC 8 (Maintenance of non-productive areas) are implemented in TK, as well as SMR 2 (Regulation on the Protection of Water against Agricultural Nitrate Pollution) and SMR 7 (Regulation on Fertilizers).

In more detail, the maintenance of permanent grassland (GAEC 1) is implemented according to common rules in all countries except TK, where this GAEC is not applied, and LT, where afforestation of permanent grassland, including short rotation forestry, is allowed. The protection of wetlands and peatlands (GAEC 2) is implemented without exemptions in only a few countries, while it is not foreseen in TK and is implemented with higher restrictions in PL, which also specifies the protection of partially drained organic soils that have not yet been transformed into arable land, and with lower restrictions in CZ, LT and LV. Particularly relaxed is the LV GAEC 2, which seems to allow the installation of new drainage systems.

The ban on burning arable stubble (GAEC 3) is implemented in all countries with some exemptions but is not relevant. The establishment of buffer strips along water courses (GAEC 4) requires a minimum width of 5 m in IT and ES and of 3 m in the other MS, while grazing along buffer strips is allowed and mulching is a management option in LT, and no restrictions are foreseen for TR.

Tillage management (GAEC 5) is implemented without exceptions on field slopes above 10% for ES. Exceptions apply to IT, where tillage is allowed for winter cereals crops, LT and PL, where tillage is allowed on slopes below 12-14%, and TR where no restrictions are implemented. Further requirements are instead imposed in CZ, where the cultivation of certain crops is not allowed in areas at high risk of erosion.

Cover crops (GAEC 6) are required in all countries except TR, PL, LT and LV provide a percentage UAA limit below which farmers have to comply with this conditionality, varying from 80% in PL, 65% in LT and 50% in LV. In other countries, there are no UAA limits for GAEC 6, but some exemptions for given cropping systems and soil types in CZ and exemptions for field slopes below 10% in ES.

Crop rotation (GAEC 7) is the GAEC with the highest number of exemptions. The measure is active from 2024 for CZ, PL and IT and not active for TR. For the other countries the measure has been active since the beginning of the programming period (2023). The use of cover crops and two- or three-years monoculture is allowed for extensive crops in most of the investigated countries, offering de facto way out of the commitment. Highest flexibility is found in LT, which allows three consecutive years of maize cultivation, but with some limitations. In addition, crop rotation must be guaranteed on 35-40% of the UAA for CZ, PL, LT and LV, and on the whole UAA for the other regions.

The maintenance of non-productive areas (GAEC 8) is implemented in all countries with few exemptions. IT activates the measure in 2024, while TR includes requirements to protect and maintain existing landscape elements, with references to terraces, while there are no restrictions on cultivated areas.

The ban on conversion of permanent grassland in Natura 2000 sites (GAEC 9) is implemented in all countries except TR and the partial exception of PL, due to the delay in defining protected areas in the country.

Tab. 6 – GAEC 1 (Maintenance of permanent grassland)

Common requirements	
Maintenance of permanent pasture compared to the reference year 2018. Maximum decrease of 5% compared to the reference year. It is prohibited to plough or otherwise modify areas of permanent grasslands. The ratio of permanent grassland to agricultural area on the farm must not decrease by more than 5% compared to the ratio in 2018. The measure is applied nationwide and affects all agricultural areas. Exemptions are allowed, subject to the approval by the managing authority, provided that an equivalent area of agricultural land is converted.	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure
LT	The measure is applied nationwide, except in cases where permanent grasslands are planted with forest (except for short-rotation plantations, Christmas trees or energy trees).
TR	Not foreseen in the national RDP (IPARD Program).

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 7 – GAEC 2 (Protection of wetland and peatland)

Common requirements	
Conversion of wetlands and peatlands to other uses is prohibited, as well as deep tillage to prevent the drainage of water. The measure is applied nationwide and affects all agricultural areas defined as wetlands and peatlands.	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure
CZ	The commitment is addressed at protecting carbon-rich soils and preventing the degradation of these sites. This standard will be included in cross-compliance from 2025.

PL	The commitment covers soils of organic origin with an organic matter content of $\geq 30\%$ and a total thickness of at least 40 cm. It is proposed that the standard was implemented through the protection of: a) peat bogs with an active process of carbon accumulation and partially drained organic soils currently located on agricultural land and not yet transformed into arable land; b) non-peat wetlands, not yet transformed into arable land.
LT	Installation of new drainage systems is prohibited, but the repair and reconstruction of old systems is allowed. It is forbidden to burn peatlands areas and to plough. The commitment will be implemented from 2024 except for peatland areas less than 10% of the UAA, but not more than 1 ha.
LV	Installation, renovation and reconstruction of drainage systems are prohibited, except where environmentally and climate friendly solutions are used. The commitment will be enforced from 2025.
TR	Not foreseen in the national RDP (IPARD Program).

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from partners investigations.

Tab. 8 – GAEC 3 (Ban on burning arable stubble)

Common requirements	
Ban on the burning of arable crop stubble, including autumn-winter cereals and rice straw. Stubble burning is allowed for phytosanitary reasons authorised by the competent authority.	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure
IT	Stubble burning is sometimes allowed following rules defined by Regional Management Authorities.
LT	Stubble burning is sometimes allowed following the prescriptions of the Environmental Protection Requirements.
TR	Stubble burning is prohibited in arable land according to the Environmental Law No 2872.

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 9 – GAEC 4 (Establishment of buffer strips along water courses)

Common requirements	
<p>The measure applies to all watercourses characterised by a continuous flow of water throughout the year. The measure requires the prohibition of fertilization and distribution of plant protection products on the land adjacent to rivers and other water bodies for a width of 5 metres and the prohibition of plantation and/or maintenance of a 5 metres buffer strip, which may also include tree or shrub species. Regions are allowed to set more stringent rules. Exemptions are applied for permanent grasslands, rice fields, and permanent tree crops.</p>	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure
CZ	The measure requires a buffer strip of at least 3m width along watercourses and 25m width on land with a slope exceeding 7 degrees.
PL	The measure requires a buffer strip of at least 3 m width along watercourses.
LT	The measure requires a buffer strip at least 3 m width along watercourses. Grazing and mulching is allowed in the buffer strip and the measure is not applicable to ecological farms. The measure will be implemented from 2024.
LV	Ban on the use of fertilizers and plant protection products on agricultural land in 10 m wide strip along watercourses and waterbodies and in 3 m wide strip along drainage ditches (gullies) which permanently contain water.
TR	Not foreseen in the national RDP (IPARD Program).

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 10 – GAEC 5 (Tillage management)

Common requirements	
<p>The measure applies for field above a certain slope threshold. Temporary furrows to convey water into collector ditches and natural riverbeds must be arranged at the edges of fields unless by implementing contour lines field works and forbidding of levelling and soil refinement after 60 days from tillage during Autumn and Winter. Agricultural operations along the maximum slope lines are allowed for high slopes under previous authorisation by the competent authority, as well as derogation on drainage work. Permanent crops are exempted from the measure.</p>	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure

IT	The measure applies for field slopes higher than 10%. Soil refinement is allowed for winter cereal seedlings. Alternatively, to drainage works and contour tillage, farmers could create grassy strips, transverse to the maximum slope, no less than 5 meters wide, at a distance of not more than 60 meters from each other and in a manner that ensures the safety of machinery and its operators.
CZ	The cultivation of crops with a low protective function (maize, sunflower, sorghum, potatoes, sugar beet, soybean) on soils with a high erosion risk is prohibited, unless by implementing soil conservation practices.
PL	The measure applies to arable land with field slopes $\geq 14\%$. The maintenance of plant cover or mulch in the inter-rows of orchards is compulsory.
LT	The measure applies for field slopes higher than 12%. The cultivation of potatoes, fodder and sugar beets, and other root vegetables is prohibited. Green cover must be guaranteed for fruit crops.
LV	Winter crops or catch crops must be sown along contour lines, unless using direct sowing or strip till methods.
TR	Not foreseen in the national RDP (IPARD Program).

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 11 – GAEC 6 (Minimum soil cover)

Common requirements	
Maintaining green cover or the residues of previous crops for 60 consecutive days within the commitment period (Autumn-Winter).	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure
IT	The measure applies nationwide, but with some regional adaptation, depending on the cropping order prevailing and rainfall.
ES	The measure applies nationwide, but the periods can be adapted regionally. The measure applies on slopes equal to or greater than 10%. For arable crops: no tillage between harvesting date and 1 st September. For fallow crops: traditional and minimum tillage soil practices, and no practices between April and June (included). For woody crops: when the average slope is greater than or equal to 10%, vegetation cover (sown or spontaneous) of a minimum width of 1 meter between October and March (included).

CZ	The measure is applied nationwide. The exemption to control weeds, diseases, and pests applies to land with heavy-textured soil in organic farming on which root crops, root, and tuber vegetables are grown. Protecting soil from nutrient loss, erosion, and organic matter depletion. Maintaining green cover or residues of previous crops, leaving the land unploughed after subsoiling or strip-tillage on at least 80% of the arable land area until 31 October. Ensuring ground cover in vineyards, orchards, and fallow land from 1 st June to 31 st October.
PL	The measure is applied nationwide. Soil cover must be guaranteed on the area constituting at least 80% of UAA from 1 st November to 15 th February. This cover can be: winter crops, grasses on arable land, winter catch crops, stubble, land covered with post-harvest residues or mulch. In permanent crops (orchards - fruit trees), a protective soil cover must be guaranteed in the inter-rows from 1 st November to 15 th February as well.
LT	The measure is applied nationwide with the exceptions: a) the requirement for black fallow seeding does not apply in areas of perennial gardens; b) in the areas of gardens and berry orchards, which are planted or renewed in the current year, the above-mentioned covering requirement does not apply; c) the above minimum soil covering requirements are optional after vegetables, potatoes, and beetroot growing. Not less than 50% of the UAA must be protected with soil covers up to 50 ha of farmland. Not less than 65% in the area of arable land, gardens and berry orchards be protected with soil covers over 50 ha of farmland.
LV	The measure is applied nationwide. During the autumn and winter periods from 15 th November to 15 th February of the following year, at least 65% in nitrate vulnerable areas, at least 55% in Vidzeme and Latgale, and in the rest of Latvia, at least 60% of the arable land and permanent crops of the holding must be covered by plants, such as seeded or planted crops, grasses, or unprocessed areas after harvest.
TR	Not foreseen in the national RDP (IPARD Program).

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 12 – GAEC 7 (Crop rotation in arable land)

Common requirements	
Crop rotation with at least one year interval (except in the case of multi-annual crops, permanent grassland and land left fallow). Farmers below a size of 10 ha, with more than 75% of the UAA cultivated with permanent grassland and/or forage crops and organic farming are exempted from the requirement.	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure

IT	The measure is active from 2024. Secondary crops are allowed to accomplish with measure requirements, provided they cover a significant part of the period between two main crops (90 days). Two consecutive years are allowed for extensive crops and tree years in mountain regions.
ES	The measure applies nationwide, but the rotation periods can be adapted regionally. All agricultural holdings must rotate with at least a 3-year interval (except in the case of multi-annual crops). The main crop must not be present in more than 75% of agricultural land for holdings between 10 ha and 20 ha. This value decreases to 70% for bigger holdings. If the holding is bigger than 30 ha, rotation must include at least 3 crops.
CZ	The measure is active from 2024. Up to 40 ha of agricultural land with bio-strips and sub-measure protection of the bird <i>Vanellus vanellus</i> is exempted. A different crop from that grown in the previous year shall be grown on at least 40% of the arable area. The main crop shall be replaced at least once in a period of 4 years on 100% of the arable area. The inclusion of an intermediate crop among the same main crop is considered as fulfilling the condition. The same crop may not be grown on more than 30 ha of arable land or more than 10 ha on soil with a high erosion risk in the following period.
PL	The measure is active from 2024. 40% of arable land must be cultivated with a different crop the year after. The introduction of a secondary crop after harvesting the main crop, i.e. a catch crop (winter crop or stubble crop or under sown crop) is considered a different crop. The same crop cannot be carried out on a certain field for more than 3 years.
LT	Cover crops are considered part of the rotation if these are sown just after harvesting and grown for at least 6 weeks. Maize can be grown for more than three years in the same field, but it is necessary to ensure at least one of the following conditions: a) ensure that the soil is covered with cover crops (in-seeded, fallow, winter catch crops) every year, after the harvest of maize until the following year's maize is planted; b) ensure at least the rotation of 35% of the crop grown in the previous year. Same annual crop shall not be grown in the same field for more than three years.
LV	Crop rotation should be observed on an annual basis on at least 35% of the arable area of the holding in which annual crops are grown. Same annual crop shall not be grown in the same field for more than three years.
TR	Not foreseen in the national RDP (IPARD Program).

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 13 – GAEC 8 (Maintenance of non-productive areas)

Common requirements
At least 4% of the arable area must be reserved for landscape elements, fallow areas with vegetation or buffer strips. Landscape elements (field margins, terrace, grassed waterway, group of trees, row of trees, solitary tree, ditch, wetland, rockery with or without vegetation) shall be protected from removal and damage with special reference to the nesting and rearing season of birds. Exemptions apply for farmers below a size of 10 ha, with more than 75% of permanent grassland and/or forage crops.

Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure
IT	The measure will be activated in 2024.
TR	Terraces and other physical structures (wind curtains, terraces, flood covers and prevention structures) should not be destroyed. Soil Conservation and Land Use Law No 5403.

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 14 – GAEC 9 (Ban on converting or ploughing permanent grasslands designated as environmentally-sensitive permanent grasslands in Natura 2000 sites)

Common requirements	
The measure provides for a prohibition on the conversion of permanent grassland to other uses within special areas of conservation and protection, unless otherwise prescribed by the competent management authority, and a prohibition on ploughing and any other work that inverts the soil layers, eliminates or ruins the grass cover, with the exception of work related to the renewal and/or thickening of the grass sward and to the management of water drainage.	
Country-specific requirements	
Country	Description of the measure
PL	This standard applies to all Natura 2000 sites in Poland, where the process of developing plans of protective measures and protection plans for individual Natura 2000 sites is still in progress. Currently, conservation measures or protection plans have been established for only 67% of Natura 2000 sites; these are the areas covered by permanent grasslands of high natural value.
TR	Not foreseen in the national RDP (IPARD Program).

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Tab. 15 shows the list of SMRs implemented in all EU countries and partially in TR. SMRs reflect the operational framework of the Bird (Directive 2009/147/EC) and Habitat Directives (Directive 92/43/EEC), the Nitrate Directive (Directive 91/676/EEC), the Pesticide Directive (Directive 2009/128/EC), the Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC). These Directives require Member States to codify European protections in National laws and to actively implement them within this network. The corresponding conservation actions focus on “Species of Community Interest”, “Habitats of Community Interest”, “Nitrate Vulnerable Zones” and other “Special Zones” defined through local territorial planning initiatives (proximity to urban areas and watercourses). These policies contribute to influencing the CAP and the environmental requirements which farmers must cope with. Generally, GAEC conditions are stricter in Nitrate vulnerable zones and in Natura 2000 sites.

Turkish legislation has not been harmonised from a consistent environmental point of view. The general approach in Turkish legislation is to protect natural resources, without specific reference to sustainability. Nevertheless, both the TR fertiliser regulation and the TR groundwater protection regulation reveal high sensitivity water issues, which are strictly tied with soil issues.

Tab. 15 – SMR (Statutory Management Rules)

Item	Description of the measure
SMR 1	EU - Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC) - The reducing diffuse sources of pollution phosphates. TR - Regulation of the General Directorate for State Hydraulic Works on protective measures for water courses No. 30941, 7 th November 2019.
SMR 2	EU - Nitrates Directive (Council Directive 91/676/EEC) - The protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources. TR - Regulation on the Protection of Water against Agricultural Nitrate Pollution No 29779, 23.07.2016
SMR 3	EU - Conservation of wild birds (Directive 2009/147/EC) - Protection of important landscape elements, trees growing outside the forest, and birds.
SMR 4	EU - Conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (Council Directive 92/43/EEC) Compliance with the conditions of a permit for the disposal of surface or groundwater water.
SMR 7	EU - Placing of plant protection products on the market (Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009) TR - Regulation on Fertilizers No. 30341, 23 rd February 2018.

Source: our elaboration on national strategic plans for agriculture from research partners.

Complex relationships between the laws and the implementing agencies and inadequate sanctions often make the enforcement of SMRs difficult. Table 16 provides information on the number of infringements of the main environmental regulations underlying the SMRs in order to understand the difficulties each country faces in addressing the SMRs in its territory, except for TR for which such information is not available. Infringements have been detected in all countries, with special reference to ES and PL. Most of the infringements relate to biodiversity regulations, mainly concerning the incorrect identification of Natura 2000 sites and other areas of special interest. Other important infringements relate to the incorrect application of the Water Framework and the Nitrate Directives, with particular reference to the inadequate monitoring of the status of water bodies and the consequent definition of nitrate vulnerable zones and water management plans. In addition, inadequate monitoring of emissions and incorrect application of fertiliser regulations in a few countries also contribute to compromising the enforcement of SMRs.

Tab. 16 – Number of infringements addressing environmental issues indirectly connected to soil health

Country	Type of infringement			
	Nature	Water	Air	Total
IT	3	1	1	5
ES	4	3	2	9
CZ	2	0	2	4
PL	3	2	4	9
LT	2	2	1	5
LV	4	0	0	4
TR	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.

Source: our elaboration on European Commission infringements records (2023).

Table 17 provides information about land use planning laws influencing soil health in the reference countries. It reveals an incomplete development of relevant regulations addressing soil sealing and land take, as well as the protection of sites of cultural heritage at the national level in IT. Conversely, in ES there exists a unique regulation facilitating the afforestation of agricultural lands at risk of abandonment and with high risk of erosion and protecting sites of historical heritage, including agricultural areas with terraces and stonewalls and other characteristic landscape elements. Key national laws regulating land use and land use changes also exist in the other countries involved in the study, with special reference to CZ, PL, LT and LV.

Tab. 17 – Land use planning laws influencing soil health in the reference countries

Country			Regulation references	Brief description in relation to soil health issues
IT			Legislative decree n. 42, 22/01/2004 introducing the Code of cultural heritage and landscape.	It aims to protect Italian landscapes and defines rules to identify and protect landscapes of public interest. The Environmental and Landscape Spatial Information System was created in light of this Code. The Code stipulates that Regions cannot plan the development of their territory with urban planning choices that do not respect the constraints imposed by the State to protect landscape assets.
			Land take and soil sealing regulation (Proposal)	The regulation of land take and soil sealing in Italy is a result of a general framework defined at national level, regional laws, and local authorities' planning policies and instruments. In May 2016, the national Chamber of Deputies approved a new law to limit land take and soil sealing in Italy. Nevertheless, this regulation has not yet been implemented at the national level. There are only regional initiatives with

				different rules and adopted in different years.
ES			Decree on the Forestation of Agricultural Plots of Land, Royal Decree 12/6/2001	The Royal Decree details the economic support to be provided for the transformation of agricultural land into forested areas. Soil-relevant objectives of this transformation are: to contribute to solving the problems of erosion and desertification affecting certain Spanish areas, to help conserve and improve soils, to help conserve flora and fauna, and to help regulate the hydrology of the targeted basins. The Decree provides details regarding the type and the extent of economic support for farmers willing to transform agricultural land into forests, the forest species supported, and the additional actions that can be financed (e.g. firebreaks).
CZ			Act No. 334/1992 Coll. on the Protection of the Agricultural Land Fund	This Act (No. 334/1992 Coll.) sets measures concerning the qualitative and quantitative protection of soil. The Act regulates land take and financial levies related to land take. The instrument also identifies the competent authorities for soil protection and the monitoring of soil risks. In § 3, the Act forbids certain actions on agricultural soils, such as pollution, degradation by compaction, drying of soils, erosion, and regulates the application of ground soil sediments. The application of sewage sludge is regulated via a specialised regulation. The Act also regulates land rehabilitation after land take, especially after mining.

PL			Regional Spatial Development Plans n0 80/717, 27/03/03	By the Law of 27 th March 2003 on planning and spatial development, local authorities at voivodship level are bound to develop regional spatial development plans. These plans help local authorities to establish local development priorities while taking into consideration environmental protection, including the protection of soils. The plans reflect the landscape audits, in which nature protection areas are delimited and assessed, and allow for the implementation of the recommendations of the National Spatial Development Plan, including safeguards against soil contamination and land use changes that lead to the sealing of fertile soils.
LT			Law on Land no 34/620, 05/06/1994	The Law on Land regulates land ownership, use, management and administration. It provides the definition of “land” - “the area of land surface and the internal and territorial waters in the territory of Lithuania”. The Law on Land sets land use conditions, i.e., implementation of statutory requirements to protect land, forests and water against pollution; soil against erosion and degradation; ecological status against deterioration; to preserve the fertile soil layer and rehabilitate the damaged land during construction works and use of mineral resources. It also defines land resource monitoring and land use planning, and consolidation.
LV			Land Management Law no. 228, 15/11/2014	The purpose of the Law is to provide sustainable land management and protection by regulating land use, land protection, administration and monitoring. It aims to create the basis for efficient use of land resources, sustainable territorial development by leveling the land use and land protection, and private interests and public needs for land use. The Law provides regulation for the land use by requesting the local authority to preserve areas with highest soil fertility suitable for agricultural activity or forestry and to plan the new settlements at the degraded or abandoned territories. The Law foresees land and soil protection by requesting measures for averting of land and soil degradation (the Cabinet of Ministers shall issue regulations

				on procedures for evaluation, criteria, selection of measures and monitoring of implementation). Periodically repeated evaluation of soil quality is requested by the Law.
TR			Act No. 5403 on Soil Conservation and Land Use	This legislation aims at protecting and improving soil quality, especially in areas deemed at risk of degradation due to climate change. It amends a number of existing laws and regulations by promoting sustainability and adaptation to climate change.

Source: our elaboration on various references from research partners.

3.4 Co-creation and sharing of knowledge and innovation

Some of the information presented above in Table 4 helps to shed some light on how knowledge and innovation are addressed at the country level. The first important piece of information is related to the relative amount of financial resources devoted to the promotion of advisory services. Only PL and LV are close to the EU average in terms of support for advisory services, while the other countries involved in the study are well below the EU average. Although important, this is an aggregate information and the promotion of advisory services is not necessarily related to soil health issues.

Along with advisory services, the OGs of EIP-Agri play an important role in co-creating and sharing of innovation. They are temporary forms of cooperation funded by the CAP within each national (or regional) plan to promote innovative actions. To some extent, OGs are the first concrete results of research projects in agriculture (e.g., projects under H2020), as they provide pilot applications within farms of new research findings. Innovative actions led by OGs do not necessarily reflect the intervention priorities of MSs, but simply open up new horizons for the development of more sustainable production, market and consumption systems.

Table 18 shows the number of OGs addressing soil health issues by country from 2014 to 2021. Out of 27 projects across the EU, cooperation on soil management is particularly addressed in IT, CZ and LT, while fertilisation management is more addressed in ES.

Annex II provides more extensive information on the characteristics of the OGs dealing with soil health issues in the different countries. It is possible to observe which are the key soil issues addressed in the contexts where the OGs operate. For instance, soil compaction is clearly mentioned as an important issue in CZ and LT, afforestation is particularly addressed in LT and LV, and soil erosion together with soil organic matter loss in ES and IT. No OGs explicitly addressing soil health issues were found in PL.

Further evidence is offered by table 19, which provides the number of living labs (i.e., knowledge creation and sharing platforms) and lighthouses (i.e., demonstration fields) addressing soil health by country. Detailed information on the living labs and lighthouses operating in the different countries is provided in Annex III.

There is some evidence of the implementation of such instruments in ES and IT, where living labs and lighthouses include both aspects directly and indirectly dealing with soil health issues. Particularly relevant is the management of grazing and pastures in mountain areas, the search for remedies to fight the risk of desertification in other areas and other issues related to land

fragmentation. In IT the only lighthouse found is represented by a demonstration farm located in the northern part of the country, where circular economy in agriculture is the dominant issue. LT is also worth mentioning here for the prevalence of lighthouses characterised by large demonstration farms implementing sustainable land management approaches by arable farms and cost-effective solutions to the management of animal waste.

Tab. 18 – Number of OGs addressing soil management issues in the period 2014-2021

Country	Cooperation actions		
	Soil management	Fertilisation management	Crop management
IT	6	2	1
ES	1	5	1
CZ	5	0	0
PL	0	0	0
LT	3	0	1
LV	0	2	0
TR	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.

Source: our elaboration on EIP-AGRI database (2023).

Table 19 – Number of lighthouses and living labs addressing soil management issues

Country	Lighthouses	Living labs
IT	1	11
ES	6	17
CZ	1	0
PL	0	1
LT	2	0
LV	1	0
TR	0	2

Source: our elaboration on EU living labs official inventories (2023).

In the context of the EU policies, how to operationalise the synergies between the soil health living labs and lighthouses created under Horizon Europe (or under the new “Agroecology Partnership”) and the various actions of the CAP Strategic Plans and their AKIS component is still an open question. Confusion arises from the fact that OG projects have many features in common with living labs, just as the on-farm demonstrations supported under the CAP have many characteristics of lighthouses. The European Commission (2021) highlights that there are two levels to distinguish when considering living labs: the ecosystem level (living lab), where multiple partners collaborate in the implementation and funding of R&I projects, and the project level (living lab projects), namely the realisation of a concrete project with a start date and end date. In the first case, OGs could be used to support the creation and animation of living labs, in the second case, OG projects could provide co-financing through the EAFRD for innovation activities that would not be 100% funded under the traditional

policy instruments for living labs. The same could happen with the EAFRD demonstration farms and the lighthouses.

3.5 Triggering new market opportunities

Short food supply chain initiatives and voluntary certifications are rarely mentioned by the countries involved in the study. This is probably because these are very one-off initiatives that rely heavily on spontaneous and informal arrangements that cannot be appreciated at country level. Instead, the existence of a national label, or Autonomous Communities labels for ES, for organic farming and food quality schemes is a key piece of information that can easily qualify the sensitivity of governments in promoting these market differentiation strategies. The relative importance of geographical indications of origins is addressed by considering the number of geographical indications existing in each country. The following table shows the prominent role of IT, followed by ES, which testifies to the potential of these territories. Here, production specifications can be an important tool for controlling production practices, including soil management.

Table 20 – National/Regional initiatives influencing the development of new market opportunities

Country	Organic farming (Presence /Absence of a national label)	Food Quality Scheme (Presence /Absence of a national label)	Geographical indications (n.)
IT	A	P	893
ES	P (Autonomous Community label)	A	401
CZ	P	A	43
PL	A	A	38
LT	P	A	15
LV	A	P	5
TR	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.

Source: our elaboration on various references from research partners.

3.6 Discussion

So far, we have provided a description of the policy instruments implemented in the countries participating in the study following the framework developed in the methodology by addressing similarities and differences. The present paragraph discusses the key policy weaknesses witnessed in the investigated countries, accompanied by some evidence from the existing literature, and then provides a crosswise interpretation of the overall strategies addressed in the different contexts.

At a first glance, the share of CAP and national funds supporting the adoption of sustainable practices provides evidence of the existence of governments with a different sensitivity to soil health issues (table 4). From this analysis, the focus is on drainage and tillage management in CZ, ES, IT, PL and

TR, land use change in ES, LV and TR, and fertilisers management in PL. This is both addressed through eco-schemes and AEC measures.

Compared with AEC measures, eco-schemes can potentially reach many more farmers and cover a larger agricultural area, as they are less binding (i.e., less ambitious on an environmental perspective). Evidence from the previous CAP programming periods shows that AEC measures and organic farming have often underperformed, mainly because of their lack of targeting and long-term effectiveness (Früh-Müller et al., 2019; Jara-Rojas et al., 2012; Lindström et al., 2020; Uthes et al., 2010). This problem may be even more pronounced for eco-schemes in the current CAP programming period. Nevertheless, it is crucial to emphasise the voluntary nature of the AEC measures and eco-schemes so that farmers perceive them as opportunities to improve their own farm management practices, although more often these measures are adopted by farmers who already implement the required practices. To avoid or mitigate this problem some authors suggest linking AEC measures and eco-schemes to private labelling systems (Poppe and Koutstaal, 2020), but this solution might only work for an elite of farmers.

With regard to the support for investments, scholars agree that there is a lack of targeting on sustainability issues (Pe'er et al., 2020). Among sustainable investments, particular attention is paid to the financing of equipment for recycling organic waste and crop residues. However, harvesting, transport, storage and pre-treatment are critical upstream problems that often discourage recycling initiatives by farmers. In addition, establishing supply chains for primary residues from agriculture and forestry is difficult and costly, which limits investment by farmers (Meyer and Früh-Müller 2020). This partially explains why the share of funds for investments in agriculture is low in the reference countries.

The lack of knowledge networks (Westerink et al., 2017) and the low empowerment of collective initiatives (Murdoch, 2000) is also seen as one of the key reasons that explain the limited diffusion of agroecological farming systems in Europe, with direct repercussions on soil health. The analysis conducted so far reveals the existence of a few initiatives promoted by OGs aimed at improving soil health, as well as a few lighthouses and living labs that might contribute to developing knowledge networks in the reference countries, offering further evidence supporting researcher in the field. In the same wave, strengthening local initiatives is practically neglected by most of the governments operating in the reference countries. Local advisory services are also inadequately supported by governments, and they appear fragmented into a multitude of private / public actors (with different aims, specialisations and missions) with the risk of confusing rather than helping farmers (Prager et al., 2017). Rather than general support, the direct provision of advisory services by public agencies is considered essential for the spread of sustainable management techniques (Klerkx and Jansen, 2010). In this regard, a recent survey conducted in United Kingdom reveals that, although advisory services are theoretically accessible to everyone, cost or lack of engagement on the part of providers represent a barrier to access, particularly for young farmers and part-time farmers (Prager et al., 2017). From here the need to combine mixed strategies, including support to facilitate access to private advisory services and facilities to guarantee access to public advisory services.

As far as the protection of the environment and the landscape is concerned, results reveal shortcomings in the national or regional (depending on the allocation of competences in each country) land use planning regulations and in the application of relevant environmental directives and laws, with a direct repercussion on the SMRs, setting the minimum requirements farmers have to comply with. These problems are exacerbated by the vague definition of GAECs in the reference countries.

This is a particularly alarming evidence, as the lack of data due to poor monitoring generates a knowledge gap that contributes to the failure to map vulnerable zones (Fenu et al., 2017; Jeanmougin et al., 2017; Musacchio et al., 2020), while the lack of transparency of the pre-authorisation procedures to introduce new pesticides on the market and post-authorisation procedures to monitor impacts creates a knowledge gap that contributes to the failure to protect target species and natural resources (Storck et al., 2017). This helps to explain why agriculture is still the main source of nitrate pollution (Musacchio et al., 2020) and biodiversity deterioration (Sokos et al., 2013) in Europe.

Moving to the policy areas of “triggering new market opportunities”, no mention was made of short food chain initiatives (e.g. actions of GPP) for the reference countries. This is illustrative of the fact that GPP initiatives on national level are relatively scarce (European Commission, 2020), although the European Commission is encouraging EU MSs to implement GPP for organic food (European Commission, 2014) and several local and regional initiatives have been launched within the EU over the last decade. Indeed, it is of common opinion that public authorities can potentially shape consumption and production trends through their purchasing power, thereby, increasing demand and changing the market structure in favour of more environmentally friendly products (Li and Geiser, 2005). Nevertheless, these phenomena are still limited in scope and do not have significant environmental impacts at the territorial level. The low effectiveness of GPP initiatives is sometimes attributed to the weak structure of the local organic supply chain, which is often not adapted to public procurement needs because of the high concentration of food and catering services directly linked to public canteens which seek high quality and low prices, on the one hand, and the fragmentation and dispersion of local organic food production, which does not guarantee a standardised and constant supply, on the other hand (Lindström et al., 2020).

Recent evidence from Sweden based on a panel data of 294 municipalities from 2003 to 2016 highlighted that national organic GPP initiatives have played a very limited role in influencing the regional growth of organic farmland compared to practice-based payments, and this is partly attributed to the fact that public authorities are unable to mandate food to be sourced locally (Lindström et al., 2020). The relatively low effectiveness of the Swedish GPP initiative compared to the practice-based actions does not really depend on the design of the policy itself, but rather on the difficulties encountered by the primary sector in taking up the new market opportunities opened by the public sector. The example of the Swedish study might provide a reason why such initiatives are not mentioned for any of the countries involved in this study.

Similar considerations apply to voluntary market initiatives. In addition to what we have discussed about GPP, there is some evidence that sustainability certification schemes face challenges, mainly due to difficulties in establishing efficient monitoring and auditing systems and due to their ambiguous impacts, i.e. the European biofuel schemes have contributed to increasing the impacts of intensive agriculture in industrialised countries (Meyer, 2017).

Nevertheless, the present study has identified successful initiatives in the creation of national labels for organic farming in CZ and LT and Autonomous Communities labels for ES, and for food quality schemes in IT and LV, as well as successful initiatives triggered by geographical indications in those countries, such as ES and IT, which are characterised by a wide variety of typical productions that have always been an expression of the cultural identity of local communities.

From the above discussion, it can be concluded that the combination of the national or regional organic labels and direct payments, which is particularly evident in LV and CZ, is a strategic form of

income support, as the most of the European organic production is still sold on the conventional market without a premium price (Argyropoulos et al., 2013).

Moreover, compliance with environmental directives, which implies the effective application of SMRs by governments, and clear and restrictive conditionality requirements for access to funds (GAECs) have been found to be strategic in making policies more effective, including those related to soil health. This limitation applies to almost all the countries contributing to the present study, albeit with some differences. However, our study confirms the claim of other authors in the field that environmental objectives need to be more explicit and strengthened for both AEC measures and eco-schemes (Guy Pe'er et al., 2017).

A final aspect highlighted in the present study is about the empowerment of bottom-up initiatives, which can be triggered through laws that recognise the role of local actors in land management and delegates the management of dedicated funds. Cultural barriers might prevent the development of such initiatives, but the most important are: 1) lack of coordination between central independent authorities and local agencies (Hunter and Nielsen, 2013); 2) limited cross-agency collaboration in evaluation and performance measurement (Newcomer and Caudle, 2011); 3) mismatch between short- and long-term strategies to support required changes (Marra, 2018). Nevertheless, the present study found a correlation with the existence of policy initiatives promoting the creation of associations directly and indirectly involved in the management of agricultural lands and the allocation of funds for investments, more than on sustainable practices. This possible correlation highlights the influence of local actors in the allocation of public funds.

Overall, there is some form of deficiency in all the strategies implemented in the reference countries, without exception. This fact leads us to point out a kind of malpractice or incompleteness in the strategic choices made by each country with regard to the management of agricultural land. Many efforts to implement sustainable practices would be nullified (Meyer, 2017; European Court of Advisors, 2021) as long as Governments, in line with the principle of subsidiarity, do not effectively implement the Polluter Pays Principle (PPP) referred to in Article 191 of the TFEU, for instance through the instruments and approaches shown in Figure 7.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis performed in this study has made it possible to identify similarities and differences in the soil health strategies and policy instruments adopted in the seven countries participating in the INTO-dialogue project. Five policy areas have been analysed in more detail.

Regarding the allocation of funds, it is highlighted that some countries focus mainly on investments, others on soil conservation practices, others on organic farming and others on the legal empowerment of bottom-up initiatives.

The conditionality requirements which underpin the CAP in the EU countries (or IPARD in Türkiye) play a really crucial role for the sustainability of agriculture. However, the analysis of SMRs and GAECs has revealed a high degree of arbitrariness and ambiguity in their implementation. Coherent and robust conditionality requirements were found especially for soil health issues which directly affect soil productivity (i.e., soil erosion), while more uncertain and dissimilar conditionality requirements were found for other soil health issues. In addition, shortcomings in compliance with the European environmental directives have contributed to jeopardising land management plans in

protected areas and river basin management plans, including rules to protect soil and landscape. Taken together, these preconditions compromise the effectiveness of the financial policies, regardless of the amount of funds allocated to soil protection measures. These summary considerations are intended to highlight the lack of a comprehensive policy framework for the protection of agricultural soils in the contexts investigated so far. What is even more obvious is that the time is not yet ripe for real agroecological policies that address soil issues according to the holistic approach mentioned in the literature. Some OGs and Living Labs have just started to implement pilot research and innovation actions in the field of sustainable management of agricultural soils, which can contribute to spreading agroecology among farmers.

Aware that the limited scope of the study does not allow us to make generalisations, the issues raised here reveal the existence of strong misalignments both within and between the policy areas analysed. However, recognising that there is not a one-size-fits-all solution to agricultural soil problems in the different contexts, we emphasise, the need to ensure compliance with environmental directives and the application of clearer and less flexible conditionality commitments at European level as a basic rule for the definition of any national or regional soil strategy.

Fig. 7 - Instruments for implementing of the PPP

Source: European Court of Advisors (2021).

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ANNEX I. Template to investigate how soil health policies are locally addressed

This template is addressed to all the partners involved in T4.1 and it aims to collect some relevant information about the policies addressed to the protection of agricultural soils in each national context. The template is divided into 5 sections, one for each policy area of action. Each section is introduced with a box providing tips on how to check how supra-national policies are addressed locally. The template is pre-filled with the Italian policies to facilitate the compilation.

Partners participating to the survey – CREA (IT), CSI (ES), CZU (CZ), IUNG (PL), LAMMC (LT), TAGEM (TR), UL (LV)

Section 1 – Incentivising the adoption of soil conservation practices

GAEC requirements and other conditionality requirements (i.e., conditions farmers have to comply with to access subsidies for the management of agricultural soils in Turkey)

Check from section 3 of the CAP National Strategic Plan (Reg. EU no. 2021/2115) the description of Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition of land (GAEC) and relevant exceptions if applied.

You can retrieve the CAP NSP from the following web page: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans-country_en.

Country code	List of GAEC related to the protection agricultural soils	Provide a short description of the measure	Provide explanation of the scope of application and of key exceptions and derogations.
IT	(add rows if needed)		
ES	(add rows if needed)		
CZ	(add rows if needed)		
PL	(add rows if needed)		
LT	(add rows if needed)		
LV	(add rows if needed)		
TR	(add rows if needed)		

ECO-schemes, AEC-measures and other interventions (i.e., subsidies for the management of agricultural soils in Turkey)

Check from section 5 of the CAP National Strategic Plan (Reg. EU no. 2021/2115).

You can retrieve the CAP NSP from the following web page: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans-country_en.

Country code	Type of instrument (ECO/AEC) and brief description	Financial support (€)	Planned area (ha)
IT	(add rows if needed)		
ES	(add rows if needed)		
CZ	(add rows if needed)		
PL	(add rows if needed)		
LT	(add rows if needed)		
LV	(add rows if needed)		
TR	(add rows if needed)		

Additional relevant national and regional laws promoting the adoption of sustainable soil management practices

Country code	Regulation references	Brief description in relation to soil management
IT	(add rows if needed)	
ES	(add rows if needed)	
CZ	(add rows if needed)	
PL	(add rows if needed)	
LT	(add rows if needed)	
LV	(add rows if needed)	
TR	(add rows if needed)	

Section 2 – Enabling participatory processes

CAP cooperation measures (Operational Groups)

You can retrieve information from operational groups from the following web page:
<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/links-existing-operational-groups.html>.

Country code	Region	Project title	Project period	Financial cost (€)
IT	(add rows if needed)			

ES	(add rows if needed)			
CZ	(add rows if needed)			
PL	(add rows if needed)			
LT	(add rows if needed)			
LV	(add rows if needed)			
TR	(add rows if needed)			

Additional relevant national and regional laws on supporting the creation of cooperative actions to improve soil management in agriculture

Country code	Regulation references	Brief description in relation to soil health issues
IT	(add rows if needed)	
ES	(add rows if needed)	
CZ	(add rows if needed)	
PL	(add rows if needed)	
LT	(add rows if needed)	
LV	(add rows if needed)	
TR	(add rows if needed)	

Section 3 – Promoting knowledge dissemination

Living labs

You can retrieve information from living labs from the following web page:

<https://enoll.org/network/living-labs/>.

Country code	Name	Description
IT	(add rows if needed)	

ES	(add rows if needed)	
CZ	(add rows if needed)	
PL	(add rows if needed)	
LT	(add rows if needed)	
LV	(add rows if needed)	
TR	(add rows if needed)	

Section 4 – Regulating the protection of the environment and the landscape

Presence of active infringement cases in the national environmental laws [DONE]

Check from the infringement database of the European Union from the following web page: https://ec.europa.eu/atwork/applying-eu-law/infringements-proceedings/infringement_decisions/?lang_code=en.

On the web page of the infringement database, you should make the following selections: List of infringements - by case, Status – Active case; Country – your country; Policy area – Environment. Then push search and a list of environmental infringements might appears.

Check whether these infringements are about: Habitat directive (Council Directive 92/43/EEC), Bird directive (Directive 2009/147/EC), Nitrate Directive (Council Directive 91/676/EEC), Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC), or other areas of actions you might think can affect soil health.

Country code	Type of infringement	Number of infringements	Average Year	General description
IT	(add rows if needed)			
ES	(add rows if needed)			
CZ	(add rows if needed)			
PL	(add rows if needed)			
LT	(add rows if needed)			
LV	(add rows if needed)			
TR	(add rows if needed)			

Additional relevant national and regional laws regulating the protection of fragile areas, the environment and the landscape

Country code	Regulation references	Brief description in relation to soil health issues
IT	(add rows if needed)	
ES	(add rows if needed)	
CZ	(add rows if needed)	
PL	(add rows if needed)	
LT	(add rows if needed)	
LV	(add rows if needed)	
TR	(add rows if needed)	

Section 5 – Triggering new market opportunities

Promotion of public procurement initiatives and farmers’ markets, denomination of origin, voluntary certification schemes

Country code	Regulation references	Brief description in relation to soil health issues
IT	(add rows if needed)	
ES	(add rows if needed)	
CZ	(add rows if needed)	
PL	(add rows if needed)	
LT	(add rows if needed)	
LV	(add rows if needed)	
TR	(add rows if needed)	

ANNEX II. OGs addressing soil health in the reference countries

Country	Sub-region	Project title	Project period	Category
IT	Piedmont	Innovation in viticultural soil management through the adoption of best practices and tools to support field activities	2020 - 2023	Soil management
	Veneto	Innovative vineyard soil management techniques and their influence on biodiversity and fertility	2019 - 2022	Soil management
		Innovative system solutions for erosion risk reduction and improved soil management in hill and mountain vineyards.	2019 - 2023	Soil management
		Innovative organic and mineral fertilization techniques in soil environments prone to compaction	2019 - 2022	Fertilization management
	Tuscany	Introduction and optimization of techniques and systems for non-chemical control of vineyard weeds	2019 - 2022	Weed management
		Production of organic fertilizers and their application	2019 - 2021	Fertilization management
	Emilia-Romagna	Solutions to reduce erosion in hilly and mountainous lands by maintaining and increasing agricultural activities through the use of conservative agriculture	2016 - 2018	Soil management
		Guidelines for the conservation of soils on the main wine-growing environments in the hills of Emilia-Romagna	2016 - 2019	Soil management
		Optimization of conservation farming systems through better management of cultivation techniques	2016 - 2018	Soil management
		Agroecological covers - Cover crops for increasing soil organic matter and containing weeds	2016 - 2019	Crop rotation and diversification management

ES	Various regions	Study of the efficacy of innovative biostimulants derived from microalgae to combat the adverse effects of climate change on tomato and wheat	2021 - 2023	Fertilization management
		Optimisation of the Segre Valley fertilisation plan in the Alt Urgell-Cerdanya area	2020 - 2022	Fertilization management
		Implementation, study and valorisation of a new eco-sustainable cereal	2020 - 2022	Breeding management
		Bovine livestock waste recovery and reuse	2018 - 2020	Fertilization management
		Transfer of a method for the control of erosion	2018 - 2020	Soil management
		Fertilization Management	2018 - 2021	Fertilization management
		Ground Covers of Native Species in Olive Groves	2017 - 2019	Crop rotation and diversification management
		Valorisation of agricultural waste into activated carbon for application in water treatment	2018 - 2020	Fertilization management
		Management of multifunctional margins in non-irrigated land for a better carbon and biodiversity balance	2018 - 2019	Landscape management
CZ	Central Bohemian Region	Implementation of new and innovative precision farming technologies in cropping systems	2014-2020	Precision farming
		Implementation of an innovative soil conservation cultivation technology for sugar beet	2014 - 2020	Soil management

		Development and implementation of progressive cultivation technology eliminating soil compaction and pesticide load	2014 - 2020	Soil management
	Moravian-Silesian Region	Care of permanent grassland	2014-2020	Grassland management
	Hradec Králové Region	Implementation of technologies for targeted water management in soil	2014 - 2020	Soil management
	South Moravian Region	Reducing the environmental burden of pesticides and fertilisers through variable rate applications	2014 - 2020	Precision farming
	Olomouc Region	Development of reduced tillage and fertilization technology for crops with low protective function	2014 - 2020	Soil management
	South Bohemian Region	Innovative precision farming technologies to reduce erosion and increase the yield of wide-row crops	2014 - 2020	Soil management
PL	All country	(Basydrill) Innovative technical solutions used in a seeder for overseeding grasslands to improve the quantity and quality of feed for ruminants and protect soils, waters and climate”	2021-2024	Grassland management
	Lubelskie Voivodeship	(BIOBIAŁKO) Improvement of the technology for the production of protein plant raw materials through the use of a product that improves the biological binding of atmospheric nitrogen	2022-2024	Breeding management
	Lower Silesian	Eco-innovations in crops (Improving the quality of cereal grains, rape seeds and legumes through innovative cultivation technology using basalt dust and sulphur)	2021-2024	Breeding management
	Zielawa Valley	Agroforestry in the Zielawa Valley (Innovative model of production, processing and distribution of herbs in the Zielawa Valley)	2018-2022	Agroforestry
LT	All country	Independent application of good agricultural practices on the farm - a virtual assistant for farmers	2020 - 2023	Knowledge creation

	Various regions	Improving soil structure and quality (restoration) using microorganisms. Reducing the emission of nitrogen compounds while maintaining plant productivity using new generation trace elements	2017 - 2019	Soil management
	Telšiai distr., Rokiškis distr. Kaunas distr.	Improvement and dissemination of innovative technologies for breeding and maintenance of larch, spruce, birch and black alder plantation forests	2018 - 2020	Breeding management
	Kėdainiai distr.	Implementation of the innovation in the technological tracks of eliminating soil compaction and restoring productivity	2022 - 2024	Soil management
		Centre for accumulation, transfer of knowledge, development of agricultural technologies and their demonstration “Gate of Innovations”	2016 - 2019	Knowledge creation
		Implementation of a multipurpose prototype of a strip seeder for increasing soil sustainability and ecological advantage	2022 - 2025	Soil management
		Using the diversity of native plant species to create natural landscape elements	2023 - 2025	Landscape management
	LV	Zemgale, Kurzeme, Pierīga	Development of a new technology for production of plant fertilizers from fermentation by-products of biogas production facility – cogeneration residue	2019-2022
Rīga, Zemgal, Pierīga		Innovative organic fertilizer, containing microorganisms	2022-2025	Fertilization management

Source: our elaboration of data from various references from partner investigations.

ANNEX III. Living labs and lighthouses addressing soil health in the reference countries

Country code	Instrument	Name	Description
CZ	Light houses	EKOFARMA PROBIO	EKOFARMA PROBIO is an organic demonstration farm where research and education became integral to the activities as well. The farm hosts other organisations' farm trials and demo events as a hub for organics.
ES	Living labs	ESPAITEC	This is a Living Lab of the Science and Technology Park of the University Jaume I, is a space for experimentation, innovation and demonstration of new technologies and methodologies.
		LABe	LABMission-driven innovation lab of experimentation, co-creation, prototyping and testing of new products, services and solutions integrating technology, to contribute to the transformation of gastronomy and food.
		ROBUST	Experimental collaboration that emphasizes co-creation in a real-world setting. Policy-makers, researchers, businesses, service providers, citizens and other stakeholders work together to develop and test new ways to solve problems in a specific geographic region. Includes 11 Living Labs that represent typical rural-urban settings throughout Europe.
		Agro-LAB	Participatory farming lab as a space to reactivate the agrarian sector in rural and peri-urban areas of Madrid.
		Trigo-Lab Innova Organic production of cereals for the agri-food industry	Strengthening dry organic farming through the efficient use of water by wheat varieties adapted to dry conditions and with greater capacity to use water resources, due to the increased development of its root system. The use of these varieties contributes to making the agricultural sector dedicated to cereals more resilient to climate change (CC), thanks to its agronomic and physiological characteristics, as well as strengthening the benefits of organic agriculture by being adapted to conditions closer to these production systems, thus contributing to the conservation and restoration of the natural resources of agricultural systems.
			Promote the implementation of precision agriculture through living lab methodology, among cereal and almond farmers, as a solution to increase its use on a large scale.

		HIGOS	OG for the design of innovative strategies in the production of dry figs. The project consists of the implementation of a Living Lab model through open community involving all users of the dry fig production and processing chain to determine, in real environments, the maturity and degree of acceptance in the application of different innovative and sustainable techniques that ensure the hygienic-health quality of this product, especially in terms of insect-related contaminations and toxic moulds.
		Rural Bridge	Development and interconnection of three Living Labs for the co-development of innovative solutions to promote the digital transition of the rural environment. Promoting practical, faster application and implementing innovative solutions, which is achieved through shortening the distance between the research scientific offer and the needs of the agricultural sector and the other actors involved, in order to finally achieve an agricultural sector that is economically viable, productive and competitive. Focus crops are olive, almond, pistachio, fruit, garlic and onion.
		Living Lab Rurales	Promotion of circular agro-forestry systems and the improvement of ecosystems in the counties of the Iberian Mountains of Southeast. It focuses on the most characteristic agricultural products of the counties in which its main actions will be carried out.
		ISAB	Operational Group incorporating information for the improvement of animal health and welfare in the Spanish dairy cattle sector. The focus of the project will be digitization and processing system that has been routinely collected within the dairy performance control and morphological qualification for integration into the breed improvement program.
		Agro-ecosystems in Andalusia region	Living Lab to promote an understanding of the function of agro-ecosystems in a historical perspective in Andalusia region. Reconnecting rain-fed cropping systems with extensive livestock through introducing traditional food and feeding management, crop and legumes varieties.
		Living Lab La Vega De Granada	Agroecology / Enhance organic agriculture and farming in the Granada Region, Andalusia
		AgroLab Project-open agriculture laboratories	This hands-on project relies on living labs that efficaciously create, evaluate and test various innovative agricultural practices. Mainly focused on agricultural activities in orchards, including fruit trees, berries and cereal cultivation. The ultimate goal is to assist, empower and educate local inhabitants, encouraging them to develop commercially resilient agroecological production.

		RBAPS - Mosaic Perennial Crops	The pilot area is located in the upland part of the Mediterranean High Nature Value Farming area of Navarra. For the pilot, a test area of 6,154.62 hectares was selected, forming part of the municipalities of Viana, Aras and Bargota, in the west central Navarra. The mosaic of land uses in the area of the municipalities of Aras, Viana and Bargota, creates a landscape of high heterogeneity which is the support of a wide range of flora and fauna species that are related to low intensity farming practices. The overarching goal of the project in Navarra is to maintain this mosaic farmed landscape.
		Guidelines for the production of organic avocado in arid environments	Coplaca is an Organization of Producers of Fruits and Vegetables that, in addition to bananas, have tropical crops. To explore and disseminate the sustainable management guidelines, it is in charge of the direct management of two farms of 9 ha in total in the south of Tenerife, where avocado and mango cultivation is carried out from a vacant land, under the regulations European organic farming.
	Light houses	COPLACA Avocado C Islands	Sustainable production of avocado and mango fruits with a minimal amount of pesticides
		COPLACA Banana C Islands	Sustainable production of banana fruits with a minimal amount of pesticides
		EcoRegion	Transition to reach local sustainable, ecological food systems in the region of Mallorca, Malaga and Valencia.
		Increasing fertility and soil quality by using beneficial microorganisms.	Application of fungal species and mycorrhizal inoculation in vivo to increase soil fertility and biodiversity. The general purpose is to ameliorate the quality of crops in the Canary Islands.
		SEAE-Spanish society for organic farming and agroecology	Joining the efforts of farmers, technicians, scientists, and civil people, to promote the improvement and dissemination of knowledge about the production of quality food based on agroecological and sustainable rural development.
		La Junquera	Organic farm and village that is being transformed into a beacon of regenerative agriculture according to the four returns principles of Common land in Southern Spain, the farm is based in Caravaca de la Cruz, Murcia, Spain which is on the border of the desert and as such faces many challenges related to soil erosion, water shortages, irregular rain events, unemployment, graying, and lack of possibilities. La Junquera focuses on building silt traps, swales, composting, limited tilling, and the restoration of natural areas. These

			practices not only help to reduce erosion, improve fertility and increase water infiltration but also help to increase biodiversity. The Regeneration Academy helps to make this transformation to regenerative agriculture.
IT	Living labs	DEMETRA	DEMETRA is a small network of living labs operating in different regions and working to provide innovative products and services, focusing on development and experimentation of technologies for therapy and diagnosis in crops protection.
		Lunigiana amica	A non-profit association providing marketing counselling that is currently joining 127 small and micro businesses active in the rural district of Lunigiana, Tuscany, Italy, mainly from agro-industry and agro-tourism.
		Mediterranean Innovation Rural Living Lab	Catalyst for innovation ecosystems for the sustainable development of rural areas in Apulia and the Mediterranean region.
		Optimization of conservation agricultural systems through better management of cultivation techniques	Main objective of the project was the protection of natural resources that support the production of food, especially soil conservation. The path chosen to achieve this objective involved the application of conservation crop systems through the introduction of agronomic techniques and practices (no-tillage (NT) and cover crops), which favoured the accumulation of soil organic matter (SOM) in the soil and the increase of soil fertility (chemical, physical and biological). Plowing and conventional management (CT - conventional tillage) represented the control.
		VARITOSCAN-Clima	Pilot Project for the identification of varieties / populations of maize and millet adapted to Tuscan pedoclimatic environments and the development of a low-input agronomic management model that reduces the necessary water supply to these crops and conserve soil fertility.
		MACARENA	Chemical input control in low impact agriculture is strictly connected to water and environmental health MACARENA aims at reducing the use of agrochemicals via crop rotation with ancient varieties and the use of hemp as corn borer trap crop both on maize and pepper.
		Biodiversity and Sustainable Precision Agriculture in Sannio - Italy	The project aims at reintroducing genotypes that represent the history and cereal specificity of the Sanniti production area, also with the aim of steering the sector towards productions that on the one hand are more in line with consumer requirements and on the other allow it to escape from the meshes of a market that is no longer profitable and unsustainable for farmers.

		Municipality of Ferrandina – Università della Basilicata	The aims of the project are: Improvement of soil fertility (soil structure; water holding capacity; mineral element availability along soil profile) and reduction of mineral fertilization input; Reduction of soil erosion processes; Improvement of plant productivity and commercially valuable fruit parameters; Improvement of farmer's income and consequent social and environmental advantages (reduction of migration, control activity on the territory by the olive farmers, landscape conservation, etc.).
		Metapontino area - Università della Basilicata	The aims of the project are: Reduction of annual irrigation volume; Definition of specific Kc to be adopted; Improvement of water use efficiency; Involvement of farmers in the use of new technologies for monitoring soil moisture; Reduction of environmental impact (nitrate and salinization); Improved knowledge of irrigation issues by technician of farmers' associations
		Santa Chiara Lab - University of Siena	Santa Chiara Lab at the University of Siena is already working as a living laboratory. This Lab is a place for dialogue and hybridization of knowledge, a facilitator of relationships between university and business, and a space for sharing knowledge and innovative solutions aimed at supporting the transition to a sustainable society and to solve issues linked to rural territory. Projects of research and technology transfer are promoted by the Lab, as well as activities of training and education and programmes of outreach and engagement. At the same time, the Santa Chiara Lab is collecting good practices in the agrifood sector that are implemented by several farmers and land managers.
	Light houses	Agrilombricoltura Terra Viva	Four young dairy cow farmers have applied the principle of the circular economy in agriculture, in the name of sustainability. They started from the problem of nitrate excess and turned it into an entrepreneurial opportunity thanks to vermicomposting that enhances livestock residues in a totally natural way. They have in fact created an earthworm farm and through the action of these animals they are able to transform, in a totally natural way, the manure produced by their cows into organic, ecological and 100% natural humus, suitable for organic and biodynamic agriculture. In addition, manure from farms is partly sold to biogas plants for energy production. About fifty other farms in the area are also involved in this project, united in a local cooperative.

LT	Light houses	Valentinas Genys Organic Farm	Valentinas Genys Organic Farmland (organic) is about 900 ha. Main crops are winter rye, spelta wheat, oat, caraway, flax, timothy grass, peas, etc. It focuses on solutions to reduce erosion and land degradation by: Sustainable soil tillage; No-tillage technology; Increased diversity / rotation of crops; Strategies of organic fertilization; Use of cover crops; Local varieties and; Legume management.
		martineliuukis	The martineliuukis farm grows cereals and Highland cattle. The main goal is to grow and present the highest quality products. The farm grows spelta wheat, oats, peas and buckwheat. The products have an ecological certificate from EkoAgros and a DEMETER International certificate that meets international biological-dynamic standards. It focuses on: Biodynamic farming; Composting; Biodynamics preparations; Closed-loop sustainable farming.
		AS Ziedi JP	AS Ziedi JP comprises of 4,000 ha of land where 1,000 dairy cows are being kept producing biogas. The biogas installation, which runs on slurry, generates 45 MW per day, the digestate is used as fertilizer, the surplus heat generated by the engine is used to warm up water, that is transported to the adjacent fish culture, producing eel and sturgeon caviar. It is an example of circular economy and operates in the following segments: crop production, animal feedstuff production, dairy farming and beef cattle farming and sales, biogas operations from biomass, fish farming, services provision.
PL	Living labs	Krakow Technology Park	One of the key actors in co-creating and implementing the Regional Innovation Strategy and promoting smart specialization and user-driven innovation approaches in the region, including farming.
TR	Living labs	Bodrum Living Lab	Living Lab located in Bodrum aiming at disseminating information and providing facilities for prototyping, user testing and implementation of value-creating innovative products also in the field of agriculture.
		Mezopotamya Living Lab	The living lab works in different fields and in agriculture it aims favouring the spread of technologies to produce renewable energy.
Various countries	Living labs	SOIL Webinar Soil Health Indicators	Network of 5 Long Term Observation sites (Spain, France, Germany, Romania, Sweden) driven by universities and field sites belonging to real farms. Aims: for a deeper understanding of the interrelationship between farm-based soil management practices and soil biodiversity in view of improving soil health and soil fertility. Provide knowledge on how soil biodiversity in turn feeds back into soil functions and ecosystem services as factors for agricultural productivity and sustainability.

		Agrilink	AgriLink established six Living Laboratories (Norway, Spain, Belgium, Latvia, Romania) in which scientists, advisors and farmers work together to create a food supply chain based on wheat production and processing with the aim to help mitigating farming abandonment, preserving rural landscapes, reducing soil depletion and pollution and, at the same time, producing local and sustainable food.
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Source: our elaboration on various references from partners investigations.

ANNEX IV. Infringements indirectly affecting soil health in the reference countries

Country	Type of infringement	Number of infringements	Average Year	General description
CZ	NATURE	2	2019	Failing to fulfil obligations under the Invasive Alien Species Regulation and incomplete NATURA 2000 networking
PL	NATURE	3	2019	Non-conform transposition of the conservation of natural habitats directive and of the conservation of wild birds directive, incomplete NATURA 2000 networking
IT	NATURE	3	2019	Failure to complete Natura 2000 sites designations and to fulfil obligations under the Invasive Alien Species Regulation
LT	NATURE	2	2020	Failure to complete Natura 2000 sites designations
LV	NATURE	4	2021	Failure to complete Natura 2000 sites designations and to fulfil obligations under the Invasive Alien Species Regulation
ES	NATURE	4	2013	Failure to fulfil obligations under the Birds and the Habitats Directive when authorizing a high-speed railway lines and incorrect designation of areas of special interest
CZ	WATER	0	-	-
PL	WATER	2	2019	Incorrect transposition of the WFD and incorrect reporting of river basin management plans
IT	WATER	1	2018	Failure to comply with the obligations under the Nitrates Directive
LT	WATER	2	2023	Incorrect reporting of flood hazard maps and river basin management plans
LV	WATER	0	-	-
ES	WATER	3	2018	Deterioration of protected habitats and excessive water abstraction, late reporting of river management plans, bad application of the Nitrate Directive
CZ	AIR	2	2017	Failing to respect nitrogen dioxide limits of emission

PL	AIR	4	2020	Non-conformity of local legislation with the Air Quality Directive and low control of emissions
IT	AIR	1	2015	Failing to respect nitrogen dioxide limits of emission
LT	AIR	1	2023	Bad application of the National emission reduction directive
ES	AIR	2	2019	Failing to respect nitrogen dioxide limits of emission and bad application of the National emission reduction directive

Source: our elaboration on European Commission infringements records (2023).

